

Abstract Book

Emirati Conference on Medical
Education 2025

15–16 February 2025

Fairmont Bab Al Bahr Hotel,
Abu Dhabi

For more information you can contact us via: NIHS@uaeu.ac.ae

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Proceedings of the Emirati Conference on Medical Education 2025

Authored by

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Conference Overview

The Emirati Conference on Medical Education, organized by the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS)—the accreditation body for postgraduate medical education in the UAE—is one of the country's most prestigious scientific events. Held on February 15–16, 2025, at the Fairmont Bab Al Bahr Hotel in Abu Dhabi, the conference aimed to enhance the medical education experience and facilitate the exchange of expertise among professionals in the field. This dynamic platform brought together experts to discuss the latest advancements in medical education, with a focus on improving training and assessment in healthcare.

Key Outcomes of the Conference

Main Sessions and Workshops

- 4 main sessions composed of lectures addressed the latest trends in medical education and ways to improve training and assessment in healthcare.
- 10 workshops provided hands-on training on effective techniques and methods in medical education.
- 43 scientific papers were presented in emerging topics in undergraduate and postgraduate medical education.

Scientific Researchers

- 21 researchers, physicians and innovators share their research as a scientific poster exhibition, showcasing the latest research trends in the field of medical education.
- The scientific research papers were peer-reviewed by a team of 5 conference scientific committee members.

Discussion Panels

- A panel discussion on accreditation was held, involving the National Institute for Health Specialties, the Arab Board of Health Specializations, and the American Council of Graduate Medical Education.
- A discussion panel on artificial intelligence in medical education was organized, with participation from the Secretary-General of the National Institute for Health Specialties and several experts in this field.

Sponsors and Participants

- 7 healthcare institutions and organizations participated as sponsors of the conference.

Continuing Professional Development (CPD)

- 14 hours of Continuing Professional Development (CPD/CME) were accredited for the participants of the conference by the DHA accreditation number DHA/MTS/ACC/25-0510/A

Conference research abstract peer-reviewers

- Dr. Mohammed Al Houqani
- Dr. Layla Omran Taryam
- Dr. Dr. Wail Ba Madhaf
- Dr. Dr. Afaf Al Blooshi
- Dr. Bushra Ahmed
- Dr. Khawla Eissa Al Hajaj

Sessions and Workshops

The Emirati Conference on Medical Education 2025 featured a diverse range of sessions and workshops designed to advance medical education practices, promote knowledge exchange, and foster professional development. The program encompassed critical topics aligned with global best practices and emerging trends in medical training and assessment.

Day 1:

The first day of the conference featured a series of valuable sessions. The opening session included a welcoming speech and sponsor recognition. This was followed by

- A presentation on the future directions in medical education by Dr. Mohammed Al Houqani, Secretary-General of the NIHS.
- A session on accrediting advanced medical education standards, featuring a group of experts.
- A session on Competency-based Assessment.

- 6 workshops, including a workshop for accreditation surveyors, clinical case design for exams, Wellbeing Guidelines, and Essential Skills for Program Coordinators.

Day 2:

The second day of the conference continued with high-impact discussions on cutting-edge topics in medical education, including:

- A session on artificial intelligence in medical education, with participation from several experts in the medical field.
- A session on Remediation.
- 4 workshops, including a session on Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs), Feedback to residents n Workplace based assessment and AI in Research methodology.

Participation and Impact Assessment

The conference was attended by 472 participants out of the 664 registered from various health institutions and authorities in the country. Out of 472 attendees, 279 responded to the post-event survey, yielding a response rate of 59%.

- The survey results indicate a highly positive reception across various dimensions of the conference.
- The venue (97%) and networking opportunities (96%) received the highest appreciation. Other key aspects, including program impact, catering, overall organization, and achievement of conference objectives, were rated at 95%.
- Additionally, engaging discussions (94%), audio-visual arrangements (93%), and the registration process (88%) were rated positively, surpassing expectations.
- The scientific content of the event was particularly well-received, with conference sessions (91.5%) and workshops (95.2%) being highly valued for their relevance and educational impact.

Statistical analysis showed a significant improvement in participants' knowledge, with an average increase of 1.5 points from pre- to post-conference. This improvement was not due to chance and was found to be highly impactful, reflecting a substantial gain in knowledge. The results indicate that all participants benefited from the conference, regardless of their starting knowledge level. The findings suggest that the conference was very effective in enhancing understanding, and future events should maintain similar formats while considering content tailored to different knowledge levels for even greater impact.

Future iterations of the Emirati Conference on Medical Education will be strategically enhanced to broaden its academic scope, increase engagement with international experts, and improve accessibility. Expanding the duration to include pre-conference workshops will facilitate deeper skill acquisition, while integrating online platforms will extend the conference's reach to a wider audience. These enhancements aim to strengthen knowledge exchange, advance educational methodologies, and contribute to the ongoing development of postgraduate medical education in the UAE.

Day 1

Session 1

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Inauguration Session - 8:50 AM - 09:15 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Emirati Board – The Way Forward

Contributor(s):

Dr. Mohammed Al Houqani,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: World-class healthcare is a cornerstone of the UAE National Agenda, reflecting the government's commitment to advancing the welfare and healthcare of citizens and residents alike. In line with these goals, the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS) was established as a national institution dedicated to leading, regulating, and organizing the professional development of the healthcare workforce, with a specific focus on specialty training.

Purpose & Objectives: This presentation will highlight:

1. The objectives of the National Institute for Health Specialties.
2. Its key roles and activities in supporting health professions education.
3. The strategic plan for the next three years to further strengthen healthcare training and development in the UAE.

Biography

Dr. Mohammed Al Houqani is the Secretary General of the National Institute for Health Specialties, which is the accrediting and certifying body for postgraduate clinical training programs in the UAE. Dr. Al Houqani is an Associate Professor at United Arab Emirates University, Consultant of Internal Medicine, Respiriology and Sleep Medicine. He served as the Assistant Dean for Medical Education for 5 years. Dr. Al Houqani is a Fellow of Royal College of Physicians and Surgeons of Canada, Internal Medicine & Respiriology. He published 26 papers on tobacco and sleep disorders, and he was a keynote speaker in various international and regional conferences, workshops, and webinars.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Inauguration Session - 9:30 AM - 10:10 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Effective Use of the ACGME/ACGME-I Milestones: Improving Assessments of Learners and Programs

Contributor(s):

Dr. James Arrighi,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: The ACGME and ACGME International have developed their educational Milestones in each specialty as a framework for postgraduate medical education programs to facilitate the achievement of competencies of learners, and as a means to assess programmatic outcomes. In this session, we will discuss how to facilitate implementation of the milestones, and how to effectively use individual and aggregate data for both formative feedback to learners and program quality improvement, including strategies to evaluate the developmental progression of trainees and to examine approaches to measure educational outcomes.

Purpose & Objectives:

1. Demonstrate how to effectively implement the ACGME-I milestones within a program's assessment infrastructure;
2. Describe how analysis of milestones data can be used to improve assessment and education of learners;
3. Understand how aggregate milestones data can be used for program assessment.

Biography

Dr. James Arrighi is the President and Chief Executive Officer of ACGME-International. He completed his Bachelor of Science and Medical Doctor degrees at Brown University in Rhode Island, USA. He completed training in internal medicine, cardiology, and nuclear medicine at Washington University in St. Louis, the National Institutes of Health, and Yale University School of Medicine. Before joining ACGME, Dr. Arrighi served as a program director for the cardiology fellowship, and as director of graduate medical education, at Brown University and Rhode Island Hospital. He is a Professor of Medicine Emeritus at Brown University, USA

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Inauguration Session - 9:30 AM - 10:10 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Advancing Outcomes in Healthcare through Education – Integrating Predictive and Learning Analytics with

ACGME Milestones

Contributor(s):

Dr. Yoon Soo Park,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: The ACGME and ACGME-I Milestones provide a structured framework for assessing the competencies of medical learners and programs. By tracking the progression of clinical skills, knowledge, and professional behaviour across stages of training, these milestones help identify areas for improvement, guide tailored feedback, and inform curricular adjustments. This presentation explores best practices for using the Milestones to enhance assessment accuracy, foster continuous development, and align educational objectives with real-world healthcare needs. Effective implementation of these tools not only improves individual learner outcomes but also strengthens the overall quality of medical education and program accreditation.

Biography

PHD is the Ilene B. Harris Endowed Professor and Head of the Department of Medical Education at the University of Illinois College of Medicine. He holds a Ph.D. in Measurement, Evaluation, and Statistics from Columbia University. Dr. Park's research focuses on data science and learning analytics, including the use of measurement science to evaluate learning. He is active in international collaborations, in both research and teaching, by organizing and leading partnerships with researchers and institutions in North America, Europe, Middle East, and Asia. Dr. Park previously served as Vice President of the American Educational Research Association (AERA) and Chair of Research in Medical Education for the Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC).

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 1 - 10:40 AM - 11:00 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Lessons Learned From 200 CLER Visits - A Field Representatives Perspective

Contributor(s):

Dr. Dale Ray,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: The presenter will discuss the ACGME CLER program and his lessons learned from conducting over 200 Clinical Learning Environment Site Visits. These lesson will address way to improve patient safety and health care quality at teaching hospitals, and also to improve faculty member and medical education learners engagement in patient safety and health care quality.

These discussions are representative of the presenter and not the ACGME or its current or past leadership

Purpose & Objectives:

1. Overview and Structure of ACGME CLER site visits
2. Initial and Longitudinal Finding from these visits
3. Engagement of Leadership, Faculty member and Resident and Fellows in Patient Safety and Quality
4. Lessons learned and presenter's recommendations.

Biography

Dale Ray's experiences spans over 30 years and includes leadership roles in Graduate Medical Education, Undergraduate Medical Education, departmental and health system's operations, practice management, patient safety, health care quality, and risk. Dale practiced clinically over 25 years at a level-one trauma center in Grand Rapids, Michigan.

Dale worked for the ACGME for seven years as an inaugural member of the Clinical Learning Environment Review (CLER) team. He conducted over 200 site reviews, leading over half. The teams provided feedback to the hospital's GME and leadership teams to improve patient safety and health care quality, and to increase engagement of GME team in these initiatives. He implemented several of the CLER program's most important initiatives and contributed to over two dozen published reports of national findings.

Prior to joining the ACGME, Dale served at every level of GME in Grand Rapids, including as emergency medicine program director, Designated Institutional Official, and CEO of Grand Rapids Medical Education Partners. His efforts as a faculty member were directed at creating solutions to vexing educational challenges. He also was the director for the Late Clinical Experience. responsible for the educational programs and policies for 400 medical students at seven Michigan State University campuses.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 1 - 11:00 AM - 11:20 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: NIHS Accrediation Journey

Contributor(s):

Ms. Wafa Al Awlaqi,

Session/Workshop Details

Description:

- Importance and centrality of accreditation
- Pillars of an accreditation system
- Review of NIHS accreditation system and experience
- Challenges, lessons, and prospects

Biography

Wafa Al-Alawlaqi holds an Executive master's degree in public administration and a bachelor's degree in communication and media sciences from Zayed University with honors. With a wealth of practical and professional experience spanning over 13 years in education, professional training, business management, accreditation processes, and quality assurance, I actively contribute to the success of the National Institute for Health Specialties.

My role within the institute involves managing and enhancing procedures and services for both institutional and programmatic accreditation. I take part in coordinating the Central Accreditation Committee and its subcommittees, overseeing the organization of institutional and programmatic evaluation processes, accrediting assessors, and preparing reports pertinent to accreditation services.

In addition, I have been a proactive participant in shaping the institute's future through my involvement in developing its strategy. This includes formulating policies, standards, and procedures for accreditation, evaluation, and training. Notably, I played a pivotal role in the successful launch of the institute's website and electronic services.

Through my dedicated contributions, my goal is to elevate medical education within the country and champion the implementation of quality assurance standards in the delivery of health training programs.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 1 - 11:20 AM - 11:40 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: overview: Nursing Transition to Practice Program for New Nurse Graduates

Contributor(s):

Dr. Ikram Altell,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: Oral Presentation explaining the aim of the program, conceptual Model, curriculum, Learners Journey, the quality insurance process of the program and the ANCC accreditation Journey

Purpose & Objectives:

To give an overview about the Nursing Transition to Practice Program

Biography

Ikram Altell is a dedicated nursing professional with a robust academic background, holding a Bachelor of Science in Nursing and a Master's in Nursing Education from the University of Jordan. She is credentialed as a Registered Nurse (RN), and her qualifications include both a Bachelor's and a Master's degree in Nursing (BSN, MSN). Currently, Ikram serves as the Head of Nursing at Emirates Health Services (EHS), where she has been leading the Nursing and Midwifery Professional Development team since 2020. In 2023, she became the Program Director for the Nursing Transition to Practice Program at EHS, which is accredited by the American Nurses Credentialing Center (ANCC) as the first PTAP RN Residency program in UAE. With extensive experience in clinical nursing, nursing education, and nursing administration and management.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 2 - 12:10 PM - 12:30 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: In-Training needs Assessment – Programmatic Assessment

Contributor(s):

Prof. Mohi Eldin Magzoub,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: In-training needs assessment is a critical component of programmatic assessment, focusing on identifying and addressing gaps in learners' knowledge, skills, and performance throughout their training. This approach integrates continuous evaluation, feedback, and reflection to create a comprehensive picture of learner development. By aligning assessment tools with programmatic goals, it ensures that learners receive personalized guidance to meet competency milestones and address deficiencies. This presentation explores the importance of in-training needs assessments, highlights effective strategies for implementation, and discusses how they contribute to improving learner outcomes, program quality, and accreditation standards.

Biography

Prof Mohi Eldin Magzoub obtained his PhD in medical education from Maastricht University in 1994 and a membership of the Faculty of Public health Medicine, Royal Colleges of physician of the United Kingdom in 2000. He is currently the Chair of the Department of Medical Education and professor, College of Medicine and Health Sciences, United Arab Emirates University. Prior to joining UAEU University he was a founding member of the College of Medicine Program, King Saud bin Abdulaziz University for Health Sciences, Saudi Arabia. He is the Chair of Central Assessment Committee, National Institute of Health Specialties. He served as a consultant to many international Institutions including WHO. He published a number of articles in reputable medical education outlets.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 2 - 12:30 PM - 12:50 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Redefining the Emirati Board Assessment Journey: WBA and Exit Exam

Contributor(s):

Dr. Teodora Elena Ucenic,

Dr. Fouzia Shersad,

Ms. Alanoud Althaibani,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: The Emirati Board is transforming its assessment approach to align with global best practices by integrating Workplace-Based Assessments (WBA) and enhancing the structure of the Exit Exam. WBAs provide continuous, real-time evaluation of residents' clinical skills, professionalism, and decision-making in their actual practice settings, promoting a holistic view of competency. The redesigned Exit Exam complements this by ensuring readiness for independent practice through rigorous summative assessment. This presentation highlights the rationale, implementation strategies, and anticipated impact of these innovations on training quality and patient care standards, emphasizing their role in redefining excellence in medical education.

Biography

Dr. Teodora-Elena Ucenic:

Graduated Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Tg. Mures, Romania, (1980 – 1986).

Previous Appointments:

2004 – 2020: consultant Ob/Gyn in governmental and private hospitals in Al Ain and Abu Dhabi.

1994 – 2004: Consultant, University Hospital Sibiu, Romania.

1/2/1994 – 31/05/1998: Specialist, University Hospital Sibiu, Romania.

1/1/1991 – 31/1/1994: Resident, Ob/Gyn University Hospital No. 2 Tg. Mures, Romania.

Academic Appointments:

2021 – to date: Assistant professor Obs/Gyn at CMHS, UAEU, Al Ain

1/07/2016 - 28/2/2017: core faculty, Chair of PEC Residency Program Corniche Hospital.

1/1/2013 – 30/06/2015: Ob/Gyn residency program director, Al Ain Hospital.

1/09/2013 – 28/2/2017: adjunct Assistant Professor Ob/Gyn, CMHS Al Ain.

22/08/2010 – 31/12/2012: Core faculty Ob/Gyn residency program, Al Ain Hospital,

7/3/1996 – 01/07/2004: Assistant Professor, Faculty of Medicine Sibiu, Romania.

1/6/1993 – 6/3/1996: Medical researcher Ob/Gyn. Center for Public Health and Medical Researches Sibiu, branch of Romanian Academy for Medical Sciences.

Personal statement:

Using a lifelong carrier, I want to dedicate all my clinical, academic, and administrative expertise to the new generations of doctors.

I wish them to become eminent physicians, ethical, strong and reliable pillars of their society.

Dr. Fouzia Shersad

Dr. Fouzia Shersad V (MBBS, MHPE, FAIMER Fellow, FRCP (Glasg.), PhD) is an accomplished physician, educator, and medical education specialist with 30 years of experience across the USA, UK, India, Oman, and the UAE. Currently serving as a Medical Education Expert at the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS) in the UAE, she works on the development and implementation of Emirati Board exams and workplace-based assessments. She also acts as a Project Advisor at the International FAIMER Institute in Philadelphia.

Dr. Fouzia dedicated over 20 years to Dubai Medical College (DMC) as Associate Professor and Director of Medical Education and Quality, leading the institution to secure the prestigious Dubai Quality Award, Mohammed Bin Rashid Al Maktoum Award, and World Education Congress Awards. She organized Annual Dubai Medical Education Symposium (DMES) for ten years, co-developed the UAE National Competency Framework for medical students (EmiratesMEDs). She led the Working Group on Assessment of EmiratesMEDs to publish the “Assessment Guidelines” for medical schools in the UAE.

A Senior Assessor for the Dubai Quality Award, Dr. Fouzia also guided DMC through several accreditation cycles and championed social programs like the “Takecare” initiative and “international away electives”.

An avid researcher, Dr. Fouzia focuses on graduate medical education, continuous professional development, workplace-based assessment, and the emerging role of artificial intelligence in medical training. Her passion lies in driving excellence in healthcare education and leveraging technology to enhance assessment and learning outcomes for future medical professionals.

Ms. Al Anoud Al Thaibani

Al Anoud Al Thaibani holds a master’s degree in food science from the United Arab Emirates University, where she gained in-depth knowledge and expertise in the field. This academic background complements her professional experience, bridging her work in both health specialties and food science, and providing her with a well-rounded skill set that enhances her contributions to the healthcare and education sectors.

Currently, Al Anoud is handling all the assessment obligations at the National Institute for Health Specialties, where she is responsible for overseeing and assessing Emirati Board Examinations for residents and fellows in accredited residency and fellowship programs. In this role, she organizes and coordinates all assessment examinations for the Emirati Board, ensuring that each examination is conducted smoothly and in accordance with established guidelines. She also ensures the proper evaluation and documentation of exam results, contributing to the quality and integrity of the healthcare education system in the UAE. Additionally, AlAnoud manages correspondence, organizes events, and handles various administrative duties, supporting the efficient operation of the institute.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 2 - 12:50 PM - 1:10 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Reforming Continuing Education for Health Professionals: Viewing it through the lens of “Systems Thinking”

Contributor(s):

Prof. Hossam Hamdy

Session/Workshop Details

Description: The relation between health professions education and healthcare systems is inseparable and complex, a ‘wicked problem’.

Health Professions Continuing Education is a critical piece for improving the quality of health care. Continuing Education (CE), Continuing Medical Education (CME), and Continuing Professional Development (CPD) are terms used interchangeably, they could have different meanings and be confusing.

In a rapidly changing healthcare system, health professionals continuing education needs to be revisited. A conceptual framework for CPD will be presented. Planning, implementation, and evaluation of continuing education need to be viewed holistically through the lens of a “System Thinking” approach.

Purpose & Objectives: The purpose of continuing education, how it is provided, and the difference between lifelong learning and counting credits of attendance required by regulatory bodies are changing to more learner-centered education and value-based healthcare. Why CPD is needed, what, how, and what is its impact are questions that need answers.

Biography

Prof. Hossam Hamdy is a Professor of Surgery and Medical Education and the Chancellor of Gulf Medical University in the United Arab Emirates. An internationally known medical educator and active pediatric surgeon. A scholar, professional, and leader in higher education, he has been involved in the development of several medical schools in the MENA region.

He is active in medical education research and has published many studies in medical education and surgery and has introduced several innovations and best practices in medical education.

His work and contribution to Medicine and Medical Education over more than 40 years has been acknowledged and won him many awards nationally and internationally. He was decorated by the Republic of France with the prestigious decoration as “Chevalier Dans L’ordre Des Palmes Academiques” / “Knight of the Order of Academic Palms” in 2011 and was awarded the WHO Health Workers Recognition Award: Health Professionals Education in 2021.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 2 - 1:10 PM - 1:30 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: "The Next Frontier: Health Systems Science for Modern Medicine"

Contributor(s):

Dr. Rizwana Popatia,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: This session delves into the foundational role of Health Systems Science (HSS) as the third pillar of medical education, complementing basic and clinical sciences. Participants will explore key topics such as healthcare delivery, population health, interprofessional collaboration, and systems-based practice. The session will highlight how integrating HSS into entire spectrum of education and training equips future healthcare professionals with the skills to navigate complex systems, improve patient outcomes, and lead transformational change in healthcare. Through evidence based literature and case studies, attendees will gain actionable strategies to advance patient-centered care and address the evolving demands of modern healthcare systems.

Purpose & Objectives:

- Recognise the role of Health Systems Science (HSS) in enhancing postgraduate medical training and preparing physicians for complex healthcare environments.
- Explore innovative approaches to integrating HSS into postgraduate education and clinical practice.
- Understand how HSS supports accreditation standards and aligns with evolving requirements for healthcare education and training.
- Discuss the impact of HSS on improving patient outcomes and fostering system-wide innovation in healthcare delivery.

Biography

Dr. Rizwana Popatia

Dr. Rizwana Popatia is the Medical Director of Mubadala Health M42, and Associate Professor at the Mohammed Bin Rashid University of Medicine and Health Sciences (MBRU). Primary role in university is leading Health System Science (HSS) curriculum.

Day 1

Workshops

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 2:45 PM - 3:45 PM

Location: Al Reem

Title: Accreditation Surveyors

Contributor(s):

Dr. Elsheikh Bader,

Ms. Wafa Al Awlaqi,

Session/Workshop Details

Description:

- importance and centrality of accreditation
- pillars of an accreditation system
- review of NIHS accreditation system and experience
- challenges, lessons, and prospects

Biography

Dr. Elsheikh Bader

Dr Elsheikh Badr is a public health physician and a health workforce expert and strategist with over 20 years' service in senior health systems and health workforce positions in Sudan and beyond. He qualified as medical doctor and obtained a postgraduate diploma in public health from Gezira University in Sudan and a master's in health policy planning and management from the University of Leeds UK. His professional qualifications included Sudan Board fellowship in community medicine and the fellowship of the Faculty of Public Health of the Royal Colleges of physicians UK. He obtained postgraduate training certificates on health workforce development including at University of Liverpool, University of Oxford, Royal Tropical Institute Amsterdam, Collective leadership institute Berlin, Harvard University, and University of California at Berkeley. Dr Badr was the Director for Health Workforce Development at the Sudan Federal Ministry of Health and President of the Academy of Health sciences, a large, decentralized health professions education institution. He also served as Secretary General for the Sudan Medical Specialization Board, the premier postgraduate medical education body in the country. Dr Badr has been widely involved in national, regional, and global health workforce and health professions education initiatives. He is currently the Chairperson of the Community Medicine Council of the Arab Board of Health Specializations. Dr Badr is also a designated WHO health workforce consultant and served as member of international expert panels convened by the WHO on various areas related to health workforce development. Since 2019, Dr Badr has been serving as policy expert with the National Qualifications Center UAE (Ministry of Education) working on the project of the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS) aimed at the development of postgraduate health professions education capacity. He is currently part of the NIHS team working in areas relating to governance, accreditation, assessment, and CPD. Dr Badr research work and interests include health systems strengthening, health workforce policy, migration, health professions education, and health workforce regulation.

Ms. Wafa Al Awlaqi

Wafa Al-Alawlaqi holds an Executive master's degree in public administration and a bachelor's degree in communication and media sciences from Zayed University with honors. With a wealth of practical and professional experience spanning over 13 years in education, professional training, business management, accreditation processes, and quality assurance, I actively contribute to the success of the National Institute for Health Specialties.

My role within the institute involves managing and enhancing procedures and services for both institutional and programmatic accreditation. I take part in coordinating the Central Accreditation Committee and its subcommittees, overseeing the organization of institutional and programmatic evaluation processes, accrediting assessors, and preparing reports pertinent to accreditation services.

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Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 2:45 PM - 3:45 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom A

Title: Case Designing Workshop

Contributor(s):

Dr. Fadi Munshi,

Dr. Fouzia Shersad,

Dr. Ibrahim Elhassan,

Dr. Asma Fatima Syeda,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: The NIHS Certified Case Designer: Hands-on Training Workshop is a comprehensive, interactive program designed to equip medical educators, healthcare professionals, and education managers with the knowledge and skills to design high-quality clinical cases for the NIHS Comprehensive Clinical Examination (CCE). This workshop combines didactic lectures, interactive sessions, and hands-on exercises to enhance participants' ability to create mature, competency-based clinical cases aligned with specialty domains and competencies.

Learning Objectives: Participants will:

1. Understand the benchmarks and best practices for clinical case design.
2. Develop skills to structure effective clinical cases and align them with competency frameworks.
3. Gain experience crafting performance evaluation tools, including checklists, rubrics, and global ratings.
4. Explore the logistics and management of CCE, including standardized patient scenarios and venue organization.
5. Receive actionable feedback to refine their case designs.

Workshop Highlights:

- Fundamental principles of CCE case design.
- Crafting effective learning objectives and assessment questions.
- Step-by-step guidance for writing, refining, and evaluating clinical cases.
- Peer learning through group presentations and open discussions

Biography

Dr. Fadi Munshi

Dr. Fadi Munshi is a dynamic and results-driven business leader with extensive experience in strategic planning, training program design, and test validation. As the Executive Director of Assessment at the Saudi Commission for Health Specialties, he has demonstrated innovation in operations, psychometrics, and cross-functional collaboration. Dr. Munshi holds an impressive academic background, including a Ph.D. in Medical Education, and has made significant contributions to research, publications, and academic activities. His leadership roles, awards, and involvement in numerous research grants underscore his commitment to advancing medical education and assessment.

Dr. Fouzia Shersad

Dr. Fouzia Shersad V (MBBS, MHPE, FAIMER Fellow, FRCP (Glasg.), PhD) is an accomplished physician, educator, and medical education specialist with 30 years of experience across the USA, UK, India, Oman, and the UAE. Currently serving as a Medical Education Expert at the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS) in the UAE, she works on the development and implementation of Emirati Board exams and workplace-based assessments. She also acts as a Project Advisor at the International FAIMER Institute in Philadelphia.

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Dr. Ibrahim Elhassan

Senior Assessment and Specialist, National Institute of Health Specialties, UAE

Dr. Ibrahim Balla Ibrahim Elhassan is a distinguished health profession educationist and oncologist with over 20 years of experience in clinical practice, academic leadership, and medical education. He currently serves as the Senior Assessment Specialist at the National Institute of Health Specialties (NIHS), UAE, where he plays a pivotal role in assessment, accreditation, and competency-based education.

His expertise spans strategic planning, curriculum development, accreditation, assessment and evaluation, competency-based medical education, and simulation-based learning. His work also includes pioneering artificial intelligence applications in medical education and assessment.

Dr. Elhassan has held several key leadership positions, including Dean of the Faculty of Medicine at Nahda College, Sudan, Deputy Academic Secretary at the Sudan Medical Specialization Board (SMSB), Deputy Director of the Educational Development Centre at SMSB, and Director of the Khartoum Breast Oncology Centre (KBCC). His leadership contributions have significantly influenced multiple institutions' medical training programs, faculty development, and assessment strategies.

An active contributor to global medical education, Dr. Elhassan is a member of prominent international organizations, including the Association for Medical Education in Europe (AMEE), the African Forum for Research and Education in Health (AFREhealth), and the WHO Global Health Workforce Network (GHWN).

His international experience spans Sudan, South Sudan, Nigeria, Eritrea, Somalia, Pakistan, and the UAE, providing him with a comprehensive understanding of diverse healthcare systems and medical education landscapes. His dedication to enhancing medical education and healthcare delivery has made a lasting impact, inspiring professionals and institutions worldwide.

Dr. Asma Fatima Syeda

With over 21 years of comprehensive experience in the Middle East, I am currently serving in the capacity of Senior Accreditation Specialist at the NIHS supporting various operations related to the digitalization of all operations under the scope of NIHS, Performance management of various services offered by NIHS, accreditation of training programs and institutions and assessments of Post Graduate Medical education. I also served in the capacity of the Associate Director and Manager of Institutional Research at the Quality Assurance and Institutional Effectiveness unit at Gulf Medical University. My professional journey includes a pivotal role as the Business Solutions Manager and Management Consultant for HSMC & Global Meditech, where I spearheaded the accreditation program in collaboration with esteemed entities like Joint Commission International (JCI) and Accreditation Canada.

Throughout my career, I have actively participated in university-wide institutional and program accreditations, collaborating with renowned international accrediting bodies such as CAA, QAA, IBMS, ACPE, WFME, among others.

Working closely with institutional management and academic/administration teams, I have successfully implemented various quality models, including EFQM, QAA, CAA 2019 Standards, RADAR, and PDCA Deming's Cycle. Notable achievements under my stewardship include securing the Sheikh Khalifa Excellence Gold Award (SKEA), DQAA, and DHDA awards for the university.

Embracing the EFQM model using the RADAR approach, I have facilitated its integration into various processes, systems, and services at the university.

My commitment to advancing educational institutions and my extensive experience in accreditation and quality enhancement uniquely position me to contribute valuable insights and perspectives at the upcoming international conference. I eagerly anticipate the opportunity to share my knowledge and engage with fellow professionals in our collective pursuit of excellence in academia.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 2:45 PM - 3:45 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Unlocking Potential: Empowering Medical Learners through Remediation

Contributor(s):

Dr. Thana Alyafei,

Dr. Rasha Buhumaid,

Dr. Ayesha AlMheiri,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: Remediating medical trainees in difficulty is a complex and sensitive process, essential for maintaining professional standards and trainee's well-being. Medical learners may underperform due to various factors, including knowledge deficits, skill gaps, professionalism concerns, or personal issues. Early identification and tailored remediation plans are critical for successful outcomes. This workshop will provide participants with a comprehensive framework to navigate the remediation process, addressing both academic and behavioral difficulties while fostering a supportive environment conducive to professional growth.

Purpose & Objectives:

1. Identify early warning signs of a trainee in difficulty and understand the multifactorial causes of performance issues.
2. Develop tailored remediation plans with clear objectives and timelines.
3. Apply effective communication and feedback techniques to support the remediation process and manage difficult conversations.
4. Implement monitoring strategies to evaluate progress and make decisions about the trainee's future trajectory based on data-driven outcomes.
5. Foster a supportive environment for both the trainee and faculty.

Biography

Dr. Thana Al Yafei

Dr. Thana AlYafei is an Emirati internal medicine consultant. She is a fellow of the Royal College of Physicians of the UK and Canada and a fellow of the American College of Physicians. She received her medical degree from United Arab Emirates University, completed her residency in internal medicine at the University of Toronto, Canada, and received a Masters' in Leadership in Health Professionals' Education from the Royal College of Surgeons of Ireland. Dr. AlYafei is currently the chair of the Department of Medicine at Sheikh Khalifa Medical City (SKMC), Abu Dhabi. Dr. AlYafei is a clinician educator, with extensive experience in postgraduate medical education. She is the chair of the internal medicine scientific committee of the National Institute of Health Sciences (Emirati board) and serves as an examiner for regional and international medical examinations. Dr. Al Yafei is

passionate about medical education, simulation in healthcare, and advancing palliative medicine in the region.

Dr. Rasha Bhumaid

Rasha Bhumaid is an Emirati physician of Emergency Medicine. She is the Designated Institutional Official of Dubai Health, Dubai's first integrated academic health system. She is also the Vice Dean of Graduate Medical Education at Mohammed Bin Rashid University of Medicine and Health Sciences (MBRU), which leads the learning mission of Dubai Health, where she oversees 37 training programs and more than 600 trainees across various training sites in Dubai. As Assistant Professor of Emergency Medicine at MBRU, she actively contributes to point-of-care ultrasound education in the Middle East region.

Dr. Bhumaid completed her residency training in Emergency Medicine at George Washington University in Washington D.C. and a fellowship in Emergency Ultrasound at Massachusetts General Hospital in Boston, USA. She is the President of the Emirates Society of Emergency Medicine

Dr. Ayesha Al Mheiri

Dr. Ayesha AlMheiri is a dedicated Family Medicine Specialist, Medical Internship Program Director, and chair of training . She earned her Arab Board and MRCGP certifications in Family Medicine in 2021, a foundation that has fueled her commitment to both clinical practice and medical education. Her passion for teaching led her to complete a degree in Leadership in Health Profession Education in 2020, a milestone that shaped her philosophy around learner-centered education.

As an educator, Dr. AlMheiri integrates active learning methods like Team-Based Learning (TBL), Case-Based Learning (CBL), and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) into her teaching. Her journey began as a Clinical Lecturer at MBRU, where she guided students through interactive TBL sessions. In 2021, she became a core faculty member in the Family Medicine residency, redesigning educational activities to foster self-directed learning and critical thinking.

Since her appointment as Medical Internship Program Director in 2023, Dr. AlMheiri has ensured trainees receive exceptional training across multiple clinical sites, emphasizing mentorship and high-quality assessments.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 3:45 PM - 4:45 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom B

Title: NIHS Wellbeing Guidelines

Contributor(s):

Dr. Rasha Buhumaid,

Dr. Seher Ahmed,

Dr. Elsheikh Badr,

Dr. Dima Abdelmanan,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: The imperative to foster wellbeing in Graduate Medical Education (GME) is crucial, as it directly impacts the quality of training, patient care, and professional satisfaction for both trainees and faculty. This panel discussion will explore the latest guidelines and strategies designed to enhance the wellbeing of individuals involved in GME programs. By examining the NIHS requirements and recommendations, we aim to address the challenges faced by residents, fellows, and core faculty associated with the intense demands of medical training and practice. The session will highlight interventions that promote mental health, and work-life balance.

Purpose & Objectives:

Participants will have the opportunity to discuss the integration of wellbeing practices into curriculum design, the role of mentorship and peer support, and the importance of leadership commitment in creating a culture of wellness. This session aims to equip attendees with actionable insights to implement meaningful changes that support the overall health and engagement of all GME participants.

Biography

Dr. Rasha Buhumaid

Rasha Buhumaid is an Emirati physician of Emergency Medicine. She is the Designated Institutional Official of Dubai Health, Dubai's first integrated academic health system. She is also the Vice Dean of Graduate Medical Education at Mohammed Bin Rashid University of Medicine and Health Sciences (MBRU), which leads the learning mission of Dubai Health, where she oversees 37 training programs and more than 600 trainees across various training sites in Dubai. As Assistant Professor of Emergency Medicine at MBRU, she actively contributes to point-of-care ultrasound education in the Middle East region.

Dr. Buhumaid completed her residency training in Emergency Medicine at George Washington University in Washington D.C. and a fellowship in Emergency Ultrasound at Massachusetts General Hospital in Boston, USA. She is the President of the Emirates Society of Emergency Medicine.

Dr. Seher Ahmed

Dr Seher Ahmad is a Consultant Physician and Chair of Primary Care at Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi. She is also the Associate Program Director of the Internal Medicine Residency Program and Chair of the Clinical Competency Committee, leading on remediation efforts for residents. Dr Seher has completed a Post Graduate Certificate in Medical Education from the University of Manchester and in recognition of her contribution to graduate medical education was awarded Fellow of the Higher Education Academy (United Kingdom).

Dr Seher completed an MSc in Medical Leadership and Service Improvement and leads on implementing the Quality Improvement Curriculum for residents. Her research areas include:

1. Evidence-based remediation strategies
2. Curriculum development
3. Resident Wellbeing Interventions aimed at reducing stress and fostering professional growth.

Dr. Elsheikh Badr

Dr Elsheikh Badr is a public health physician and a health workforce expert and strategist with over 20 years' service in senior health systems and health workforce positions in Sudan and beyond. He qualified as medical doctor and obtained a postgraduate diploma in public health from Gezira University in Sudan and a master's in health policy planning and management from the University of Leeds UK. His professional qualifications included Sudan Board fellowship in community medicine and the fellowship of the Faculty of Public Health of the Royal Colleges of physicians UK. He obtained postgraduate training certificates on health workforce development including at University of Liverpool, University of Oxford, Royal Tropical Institute Amsterdam, Collective leadership institute Berlin, Harvard University, and University of California at Berkeley. Dr Badr was the Director for Health Workforce Development at the Sudan Federal Ministry of Health and President of the Academy of Health sciences, a large, decentralized health professions education institution. He also served as Secretary General for the Sudan Medical Specialization Board, the premier postgraduate medical education body in the country. Dr Badr has been widely involved in national, regional, and global health workforce and health professions education initiatives. He is currently the Chairperson of the Community Medicine Council of the Arab Board of Health Specializations. Dr Badr is also a designated WHO health workforce consultant and served as member of international expert panels convened by the WHO on various areas related to health workforce development. Since 2019, Dr Badr has been serving as policy expert with the National Qualifications Center UAE (Ministry of Education) working on the project of the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS) aimed at the development of postgraduate health professions education capacity. He is currently part of the NIHS team working in areas relating to governance, accreditation, assessment, and CPD. Dr Badr research work and interests include health systems strengthening, health workforce policy, migration, health professions education, and health workforce regulation.

Dr. Dima Abdelmanan

Dr. Dima Abdelmanan, is a Consultant Endocrinologist at the Dubai Diabetes Center at Dubai Health. Dr. Abdelmanan has dual boards from both the UK and the USA. In the United States she completed her internal medicine residency training from the Cleveland Clinic Health System and then completed fellowship training in Endocrinology, Diabetes and Metabolism at Case Western Reserve University, in Cleveland. She continued to do clinical and Research work at the same institution before returning to Dubai, UAE to hold an academic position. Her research work is in the fields of

pituitary and adrenal diseases as well as diabetes. She has presented her work at national American meetings and published it in peer-reviewed journals. Besides being interested in Clinical Endocrinology and Research she has been interested in Medical Education and therefore took this leading role at the medical school in order to improve the standards of medical education in Dubai and the UAE. Dr. Abdelmannan is a scholar of the Harvard Macy Institute of Health professionals as educators and has a Masters in Health Professions Education from MGH, Boston. She is actively involved in implementing efficient ways in medical pedagogy including simulation and e-learning. Dr. Dima has led the transformation of the medical internship curriculum into a competency based curriculum under the leadership of the MBRU GME team, she also led several program enrichment initiatives such as the trainee wellbeing course. She recently took on the role of Director of new programs and accreditation at MBRU.

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 3:45 PM - 4:45 PM

Location: Al Reem

Title: Essential Skills for Program Coordinators

Contributor(s):

Ms. Wafa Al Awlaqi,

Ms. Ayah Eshbair,

Session/Workshop Details

Description:

- 1- Introduction
2. Role of program coordinators
3. Essential Skills for Program Coordinators
4. Challenges facing Program Coordinators
5. Strategies for Enhancing the Resident and Fellow Experience: Policies and Procedures for medical education programs.
6. Case Studies and Best Practices- Reem
7. Resources and Tools for Program Coordinators
8. Q&A and Closing Remarks

Biography

Ms. Wafa Al Awlaqi

Wafa Al-Alawlaqi holds an Executive master's degree in public administration and a bachelor's degree in communication and media sciences from Zayed University with honors. With a wealth of practical and professional experience spanning over 13 years in education, professional training, business management, accreditation processes, and quality assurance, I actively contribute to the success of the National Institute for Health Specialties.

My role within the institute involves managing and enhancing procedures and services for both institutional and programmatic accreditation. I take part in coordinating the Central Accreditation Committee and its subcommittees, overseeing the organization of institutional and programmatic evaluation processes, accrediting assessors, and preparing reports pertinent to accreditation services.

In addition, I have been a proactive participant in shaping the institute's future through my involvement in developing its strategy. This includes formulating policies, standards, and procedures for accreditation, evaluation, and training. Notably, I played a pivotal role in the successful launch of the institute's website and electronic services.

Through my dedicated contributions, my goal is to elevate medical education within the country and champion the implementation of quality assurance standards in the delivery of health training programs.

Ms. Ayah Eshbair

Ayah H. I. Eshbair is an Evaluation and Quality Specialist at the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS), enhancing accreditation standards for residency and fellowship programs across various health specialties in the UAE. She is also an administrator at the Commission for Academic Accreditation (CAA), working to elevate education quality nationwide. With a Doctor of Pharmacy from UAE University, she is committed to expanding clinical pharmacy residency programs and aligning them with NIHS standards. Passionate about learning and teaching, she actively contributes to advancing healthcare education.

Ms. Fatima Al Mehari

Date: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 2:45 PM - 3:45 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom A

Title: Enhancing Quality of AI Generated Items

Contributor(s):

Dr. Fadi Munshi,

Dr. Asma Fatima Syeda,

Dr. Hadeel Abd Elkarim,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: Workshop will equip medical educators with the knowledge and skills to effectively integrate AI into their item writing process, enhancing the quality and efficiency of assessments in medical education.

Intended Outcomes

At the end of the workshop, the participants will be able.

- To introduce participants to the principles of effective item writing in assessments, focusing on creating high quality, valid, and reliable questions.
- To explore the application of artificial intelligence (AI) in developing and refining assessment items.
- To provide hands-on experience utilizing AI tools for generating and analyzing assessment items.
- To discuss the potential challenges and ethical considerations in using AI for item writing in medical education

Workshop Components

- Introduction to AI in Assessment: An overview of how AI can be integrated into the assessment process, focusing on item writing.
- Principles of Effective Item Writing: A review of best practices in crafting assessment items that are fair, clear, and aligned with learning objectives.
- Interactive AI Demonstration: A session will be held where participants will observe a demonstration of the steps of item generation using AI.
- Item Generation and Critique Using AI: A hands-on session where participants will engage with AI tools to create an initial draft followed by a structured evaluation of items in groups.

Biography

Dr. Fadi Munshi

Dr. Fadi Munshi is a dynamic and results-driven business leader with extensive experience in strategic planning, training program design, and test validation. As the Executive Director of Assessment at the

Saudi Commission for Health Specialties, he has demonstrated innovation in operations, psychometrics, and cross-functional collaboration. Dr. Munshi holds an impressive academic background, including a Ph.D. in Medical Education, and has made significant contributions to research, publications, and academic activities. His leadership roles, awards, and involvement in numerous research grants underscore his commitment to advancing medical education and assessment.

Dr. Asma Fatima Syeda

With over 21 years of comprehensive experience in the Middle East, I am currently serving in the capacity of Senior Accreditation Specialist at the NIHS supporting various operations related to the digitalization of all operations under the scope of NIHS, Performance management of various services offered by NIHS, accreditation of training programs and institutions and assessments of Post Graduate Medical education. I also served in the capacity of the Associate Director and Manager of Institutional Research at the Quality Assurance and Institutional Effectiveness unit at Gulf Medical University. My professional journey includes a pivotal role as the Business Solutions Manager and Management Consultant for HSMC & Global Meditech, where I spearheaded the accreditation program in collaboration with esteemed entities like Joint Commission International (JCI) and Accreditation Canada.

Throughout my career, I have actively participated in university-wide institutional and program accreditations, collaborating with renowned international accrediting bodies such as CAA, QAA, IBMS, ACPE, WFME, among others.

Working closely with institutional management and academic/administration teams, I have successfully implemented various quality models, including EFQM, QAA, CAA 2019 Standards, RADAR, and PDCA Deming's Cycle. Notable achievements under my stewardship include securing the Sheikh Khalifa Excellence Gold Award (SKEA), DQAA, and DHDA awards for the university.

Embracing the EFQM model using the RADAR approach, I have facilitated its integration into various processes, systems, and services at the university.

My commitment to advancing educational institutions and my extensive experience in accreditation and quality enhancement uniquely position me to contribute valuable insights and perspectives at the upcoming international conference. I eagerly anticipate the opportunity to share my knowledge and engage with fellow professionals in our collective pursuit of excellence in academia.

Dr. Hadeel Abd Elkarim,

Dr. Hadeel Aboueisha is an internal medicine physician and Senior assessment Specialist in NIHS. She also plays a role as an Assessments Specialist at the National Institute of Health Specialties in the UAE, where she focuses on enhancing assessment processes through AI modalities. Her work supports the advancement of medical education and clinical practice, with a particular interest in integrating innovative technologies to improve assessment and training.

Day 2

Sessions

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 3 - 8:45 AM - 9:05 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: AI in Medical Education

Contributor(s):

Dr. Mohammed Al Houqani,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: Artificial Intelligence (AI) is transforming medical education by revolutionizing how healthcare professionals are trained and assessed. AI enables personalized learning experiences and real-time feedback, creating tailored educational pathways that address the unique needs of learners. In postgraduate medical education, AI facilitates the development of innovative assessment tools, ensuring precision and fairness. Additionally, AI supports curriculum development by identifying competency gaps and optimizing resource allocation. By bridging undergraduate and postgraduate training, AI fosters a seamless transition across education stages, enhancing the continuity of learning. Its integration into medical education demonstrates immense potential to elevate the quality, efficiency, and accessibility of training, ultimately driving advancements in healthcare practice and knowledge dissemination.

Biography

Dr. Mohammed Al Houqani is the Secretary General of the National Institute for Health Specialties, which is the accrediting and certifying body for postgraduate clinical training programs in the UAE. Dr. Al Houqani is an Associate Professor at United Arab Emirates University, Consultant of Internal Medicine, Respiriology and Sleep Medicine. He served as the Assistant Dean for Medical Education for 5 years. Dr. Al Houqani is a Fellow of Royal College of Physicians and Surgeons of Canada, Internal Medicine & Respiriology. He published 26 papers on tobacco and sleep disorders, and he was a keynote speaker in various international and regional conferences, workshops, and webinars.

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 3 - 9:05 AM - 9:25 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Big Data Management in the era of Artificial Intelligence

Contributor(s):

Prof. Fikri M Abu-Zidan,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: Planning, effective governance, infrastructure changes, and proper data management will enhance the role of big data and AI. Ethical AI principles include 1) do not harm, 2) do good, 3) respect patient's autonomy, 4) fairness and equity, and 5) data privacy, sharing, and transparency. Ethical, legal, administrative, technical, and economical challenges will be encountered during this process. Future healthcare systems should be transparent, ethical, accountable, and sustainable, which has high quality and equity of care. The success of digital big data and AI depends on adopting multidisciplinary teamwork, collaborating, learning, and addressing challenges together to improve patients' health care.

Purpose & Objectives:

The use of big data and artificial intelligence (AI) may impact our future clinical practice. Big data and AI can support clinical decision-making in prediction and prognosis, give alarms during emergency situations, and improve healthcare communication between patients, nurses and doctors. The presentation will highlight the role of big data on clinical practice in the era of artificial intelligence and point-out its limitations.

Biography

Professor Fikri Abu-Zidan: An international expert in Statistics, Research Methodology, Acute Care Surgery, Disaster Medicine, and Point-of-Care Ultrasound. He graduated (MD) from Aleppo University (Syria) in 1981; gained the FRCS, Glasgow, Scotland in 1987; achieved his PhD in Trauma and Disaster Medicine from Linkoping University (Sweden) in 1995; and obtained his Postgraduate Diploma of Applied Statistics from Massey University (New Zealand) in 1999. He is currently serving as a Statistics and Research Methodology Consultant for the World Society of Emergency Surgery. He has made major contributions to trauma and acute care surgery management, education and research in Kuwait, Sweden, New Zealand, Australia, and United Arab Emirates. He has more than 515 publications in books and refereed international journals. He presented more than 830 invited lectures and scientific abstracts, chaired more than 80 scientific sessions, and received more than 40 national and international awards for clinical, research and educational activities.

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 3 - 9:25 AM - 9:45 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: AI-Driven Instruction: Innovating Design and Content Creation"

Contributor(s):

Dr. Shifan Khanday,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: "AI-Driven Instruction: Innovating Design and Content Creation" is designed to empower educators and instructional designers with the tools and knowledge to integrate AI into their work. This workshop covers the basics of AI in education, focusing on how AI can personalize learning experiences, enhance content creation, and drive data-informed decision-making. Participants will explore AI-driven tools, engage in hands-on activities, and discuss ethical considerations. By the end of the workshop, attendees will be equipped to innovate in instructional design and content creation, leading the future of education with AI.

Purpose & Objectives:

Explore the fundamentals of AI and its applications in education.

Explore AI tools for personalized learning and adaptive instruction.

Learn to utilize AI-driven platforms for creating dynamic and interactive content.

Analyze educational data with AI to improve instructional strategies.

Discuss ethical considerations in the use of AI in education.

Apply practical skills to integrate AI into instructional design and content creation processes

Biography

Dr. Shifan Khanday is a distinguished medical professional and educator, currently serving as the Director of eLearning and Acting Associate Dean of Research at Dubai Medical College for Girls. With a multifaceted academic background and a commitment to advancing medical education, Dr. Khanday is a leading figure in the integration of technology and education within the healthcare sector.

Dr. Khanday holds an MBBS and MD, complemented by a Diplomate in Family Medicine, reflecting her comprehensive understanding of clinical practice. Her pursuit of excellence in education led her to earn a Master's in Health Professions Education (MHPE), enhancing her ability to innovate in teaching and curriculum design.

Dr. Khanday has expanded her expertise to include an MBA, equipping her with strategic management skills that are crucial in her leadership roles. Recognizing the transformative potential of technology in healthcare, she further pursued a Master's in Artificial Intelligence.

As Director of eLearning, Dr. Khanday has been instrumental in driving the digital transformation at DMCG. Acting Associate Dean of Research, she oversees a dynamic research environment, fostering innovation and encouraging the development of new knowledge in medicine.

Dr. Khanday is a passionate advocate for the integration of AI in medical education .

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 4 - 10:45 AM - 11:05 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Turning Challenges into Success: A Strategic Approach to Resident Remediation

Contributor(s):

Mrs. Ziyana Alkhusaibi,

Session/Workshop Details

Description:

- Key components of an effective remediation plan
- Tailoring remediation plans to individual needs
- Setting measurable goals and timelines

Purpose & Objectives:

Understand and outline the essential elements of an effective remediation plan, including structured assessments, clear communication, and defined support mechanisms.

Learn how to tailor remediation strategies to address the unique challenges and needs of individual residents, ensuring a personalized and targeted approach.

Develop the skills to set specific, achievable goals and realistic timelines for remediation, allowing for progress tracking and accountability.

Biography

Mrs. Ziyana Alkhusaibi

I hold a Bachelor of Science (Honors) degree in Children's Nursing, which I earned in 2006 from Salford University in the United Kingdom.

Currently I serve as the manager of Graduate Medical Education at Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi in the UAE, overseeing all administrative aspects related to regulatory, compliance, and accreditation activities for the institution and its training programs. I have established and implemented Graduate Medical Education (GME) policies, procedures, and departmental goals in alignment with these regulatory requirements. Additionally, I provide guidance and expertise to new Program Coordinators and Program Directors on GME data systems and processes.

In my previous role as a Post Graduate Medical Education Officer at the Department of Health in Abu Dhabi, I played a key role in developing the application processes for the Residency and Fellowship Match, optimizing the placement of graduate physicians into postgraduate training programs throughout Abu Dhabi.

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 4 - 11:05 AM - 11:25 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Innovative Approaches to Remediating Professionalism

Contributor(s):

Dr. Seher Ahmad,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: This session provides program directors and residency faculty with advanced strategies for effectively remediating professionalism lapses among residents. Participants will explore techniques for identifying and addressing lapses in this core competency, focusing on evidence-based practices and case studies. The session will equip attendees with practical tools and insights to enhance their remediation efforts and support residents in achieving professional growth.

Purpose & Objectives:

1. Analyze common professionalism lapses in residents and their implications for clinical practice and training.
2. Apply evidence-based strategies to design and implement effective remediation plans tailored to individual resident needs.
3. Facilitate constructive feedback and mentorship to support residents' professional development and address recurring issues.
4. Develop a comprehensive framework for integrating remediation strategies into residency programs to promote long-term professional growth and excellence.

Biography

Dr Seher Ahmad is a Consultant Physician and Chair of Primary Care at Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi. She is also the Associate Program Director of the Internal Medicine Residency Program and Chair of the Clinical Competency Committee, leading on remediation efforts for residents. Dr Seher has completed a Post Graduate Certificate in Medical Education from the University of Manchester and in recognition of her contribution to graduate medical education was awarded Fellow of the Higher Education Academy (United Kingdom).

Dr Seher completed an MSc in Medical Leadership and Service Improvement and leads on implementing the Quality Improvement Curriculum for residents. Her research areas include:

1. Evidence-based remediation strategies
2. Curriculum development
3. Resident Wellbeing Interventions aimed at reducing stress and fostering professional growth.

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 4 - 11:25 AM - 11:45 AM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Navigating the Rough Waters: Turning Trainee Struggles into Triumphs

Contributor(s):

Dr. Safia Rehman

Session/Workshop Details

Description: An engaging and interactive session designed for educators and mentors providing a practical approach with actionable strategies and tools to support struggling trainees. The workshop explores ways to address and overcome challenges faced by medical trainees.

Purpose & Objectives:

1. Identifying the challenges and common issues encountered by trainees.
2. How to spot a trainee in difficulty early.
3. Ways to develop support plans exploring methods for creating personalised learning and offering targeted support.
4. How to use effective communication techniques for providing constructive feedback to develop an open and supportive environment.
5. Implementing solutions and encouraging growth.
6. Ways to motivate and build resilience in trainees.

Biography

Dr. Safia Rehman is a Consultant Radiologist and Nuclear Medicine Physician at Sheikh Shakhbout Medical City (SSMC) in Abu Dhabi. With a Postgraduate Certificate in Medical Education from the University of Dundee, she blends her passion for teaching with her clinical work. She previously trained at Oxford University Hospitals and was a consultant at University Hospitals Birmingham. Her expertise includes hybrid imaging, nuclear cardiology, neurological nuclear medicine, radionuclide therapies, and general/emergency radiology. She was a Fellow of the Royal College of Radiologists, United Kingdom and completed her MSc in Nuclear Medicine from King's College London, UK.

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Session 4 - 11:45 AM - 12:05 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: Resident in difficulties

Contributor(s):

Dr. Maryam Ali Al Qaydi,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: Trainers facing difficulties are a common occurrence in training programs and often demand significant time and effort to address. It is essential for faculty members and institutional leaders to be equipped and trained to effectively address and manage these concerns.

Purpose & Objectives:

- Define the Concept of a trainer in Difficulty
- Recognize Early Warning Signs
- Offer Practical Guidelines
- Apply Lessons to Real-World Scenarios

Biography

Dr. Maryam Ali Al Qaydi

Head of medical education department in Sheikh Khalifa Hospital in Fujairah

ACGME IRC membership for surgical specialty 2021

- o Member of Central Accreditation Committee of National Institute for Health Specialties.
- o Member of ENT Committee of the National Institute for Health Specialties.
- o Member of Surveyors sub-committee of National Institute for Health Specialties.
- o Adjunct associate professor in the College of medicine and health science, UAE University from 2022.

Day 2

Workshops

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 1:15 PM - 2:15 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom A

Title: Innovative Teaching Methods in Residency Training Through Simulation & Virtual Reality

Contributor(s):

Dr. Aiman Smer,

Dr. Mark McCarthy,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: This 90-minute workshop is designed to explore innovative teaching methods in postgraduate medical education, with a specific focus on enhancing residency & fellowship training through simulation, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR). The session will provide an overview of the latest advancements in these technologies, discuss their application in clinical training, and offer hands-on experience with these tools. Participants will engage in interactive discussions, explore case studies, and collaborate in small groups to develop strategies for integrating these methods into their training programs.

Purpose & Objectives:

By the end of this workshop, participants (PD/APD & CF) will be able to:

- Understand the role of simulation, VR, and AR in enhancing clinical skills and decision-making in residency & fellowship training.
- Identify best practices for integrating simulation, VR, and AR into residency & fellowship curricula.
- Experience hands-on demonstrations of VR and AR tools and discuss their practical application in postgraduate medical education.
- Develop strategies for overcoming challenges in implementing these innovative teaching methods in their programs.

Biography

Dr. Aiman Smer

Dr. Aiman Smer, is a Consultant Cardiologist and Associate Professor of Medicine at Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi, where he also serves as the Cardiology Fellowship Program Director. Before joining Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi, he spent a decade in the United States as Academic Cardiologist at Creighton University and as Associate Program Director for the Cardiovascular Fellowship at Creighton University Medical Center, Omaha, Nebraska.

A native of Libya, Dr. Aiman earned his medical degree from the University of Tripoli and completed his postgraduate training in Internal Medicine and Cardiology at Creighton University. He holds multiple American Board certifications, including internal medicine, cardiovascular diseases, echocardiography, and nuclear cardiology.

Dr. Aiman's research focuses on quality improvement, atrial fibrillation, the impact of sleep apnea on heart disease, and 3D echocardiography. He has contributed to numerous international trials and has over 100 publications and abstracts in peer-reviewed journals. A Fellow of both the American College of Cardiology and the American Society of Echocardiography, he is a sought-after speaker at national and international conferences.

Residing in Abu Dhabi with his wife and four children, Dr. Aiman enjoys family time, community volunteering, sports, and exploring Abu Dhabi's attractions.

Dr. Mark McCarthy

An Emergency Nurse and Clinical Educator with 20 years nursing experience. Currently, serving as Manager for the Multidisciplinary Simulation and Life Support Centre at CCAD. With a passion for Simulation and Education, Mark and his team are dedicated to enhancing patient care through innovative simulation education techniques.

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 1:15 PM - 3:15 PM

Location: Al Reem

Title: Introduction to Research in Medical Education Workshop

Contributor(s):

Prof. Fikri M Abu-Zidan,

Session/Workshop Details

Summary of the Course objectives:

- Guide the audience on the methods of defining feasible medical educational research questions that can be answered.
- Guide the audience on the basics of writing a review article.
- Guide the audience on the methods of designing a survey/questionnaire
- Explain the basics of qualitative research
- Structure a plan for proper statistical analysis
- Guide the participants of the plan for writing a medical education paper

Biography

Professor Fikri Abu-Zidan: An international expert in Statistics, Research Methodology, Acute Care Surgery, Disaster Medicine, and Point-of-Care Ultrasound. He graduated (MD) from Aleppo University (Syria) in 1981; gained the FRCS, Glasgow, Scotland in 1987; achieved his PhD in Trauma and Disaster Medicine from Linkoping University (Sweden) in 1995; and obtained his Postgraduate Diploma of Applied Statistics from Massey University (New Zealand) in 1999. He is currently serving as a Statistics and Research Methodology Consultant for the World Society of Emergency Surgery. He has made major contributions to trauma and acute care surgery management, education and research in Kuwait, Sweden, New Zealand, Australia, and United Arab Emirates. He has more than 515 publications in books and refereed international journals. He presented more than 830 invited lectures and scientific abstracts, chaired more than 80 scientific sessions, and received more than 40 national and international awards for clinical, research and educational activities.

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 2:15 PM - 3:15 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom A

Title: Workplace Based Assessment (WBA): Delivering Feedback to Learners

Contributor(s):

Dr. Shamsa Abdulmanan Abdulrahman Mohammed Al Awar,

Dr. Gehan Sayed Sallam,

Ms. Sara Maki,

Session/Workshop Details

Description: Delivering feedback is a complex process with many influencing factors. The feedback process engages the learner with information about their performance quality and leads to improvement in learning strategies. Feedback supports learners' effective decision-making and helps to improve learning outcomes. When providing feedback, it is important to use various techniques and tools tailored to the individual learner and situation. There are various reflective feedback techniques, including direct observation, real-time feedback, self-assessment, multiple sources, and other specialized techniques. One of the most popular models related to reflective practice (PR) feedback is Pendleton's model (1984), "reflection for action."

Purpose & Objectives:

Intended Outcomes

At the end of the workshop, the participants will be able to:

- Understand Miller's Pyramid and its relevance to clinical education
- Comprehend the concept and significance of Workplace-Based Assessments (WBA)
- Grasp the concept of Reflective Practice Feedback within clinical settings:
- Learn and apply effective feedback models, with a focus on Pendleton's Rules
- Identify and overcome barriers to effective Reflective Practice Feedback

Biography

Dr. Shamsa Abdulmanan Abdulrahman Mohammed Al Awar

Dr. Shamsa is a Senior Consultant in Obstetrics and Gynecology & Chair of Ob/Gyn department, college of Medicine & health Sciences at UAE University, the Vice Chair of UAE Higher Medical Liability Committee, Chair of Women and Child Health Advisory Group in Abu Dhabi and member of Emirati Medical Council in Department of Health AD.

Dr. Shamsa graduated with distinctions from Sultan Qaboos University with Bch of Medical Sciences and MD. She persuaded her postgraduate studies at McGill University, Montreal in Canada and graduated with Alice Benjamin Award of Excellence in Obstetrics. She has the Fellowship in Ob/Gyn from Royal College of Physicians & Surgeons of Canada (FRCSC), American Board in OB/Gyn & Fellowship of American Congress in OB/Gyn, Fellowship of American Board in Hospital Management

(FABC), Fellowship of American Board in Medical Quality and Certified American Medicolegal Consultant.

Dr Shamsa is a highly caliber award winning women advocate for which her excellency was identified through “Alice Benjamin” Award of Excellence in Obstetrics, AD Medical Award in Clinical performance, Sh. Shamsa Bint Suhail Creative women Award, Arab Women Award- medical, Women UAE Volunteers and UAEU Chancellor’s Medal for the community work.

Dr. Gehan Sayed Sallam

Dr Gehan Sallam, currently working as clinical research nurses at OB/Gyn, UAEU, She Joined the academic field since 2017. Gehan completed her Bachelor since of nursing Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt in 1996, then earned her Master degree at 2016 and PhD at 2022 form the same university. Gehan has great experience in nursing field started as critical care nurse at Egypt, worked in different hospitals abroad such as at King Dom of Saudi Arabia, UAE and Egypt. She was Certified Diabetes Educator from Leicester University UK, specialized as CDE, she uses all of her teaching modalities to teach different categories such as; (patient, family, health care professional, medical and nursing student). Gehan developed & designed many patient and family education leaflet in both language Arabic & English along with coordination of many community outreach program. She has good experience as an examiner for medical student for many OSCE & MiniCex exam. She coordinated and contributed in many scientific researches. Being speaker in many conferences in Congress on Endometriosis and Uterine Disorder at January 2024 workshop title (Role of Nurses in Patient Quality of Life with Endometriosis).

Ms. Sara Maki

I’m Sara Maki, currently working as a Medical Research Specialist at OB/Gyn Department, CMHS , UAEU, I Joined UAEU-CMHS since 2014. I completed my Bachelor's science degree as a Medical Lab Technologist, University of Sharjah, UAE, Diploma in Health Management, American Institute of Healthcare and Hospital Management. Fellowship in Molecular Biology of Gonadotropins and Sex Steroid Hormones, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Modena, Italy-2023. International Board-Certified Lactation Consultant-2022. Basic life support (BLS) instructor -2021

I have good experience as an examiner for medical students for many OSCE & MiniCex exams. I coordinated, contributed, and played a main role in many scientific researches. Being a speaker at many conferences such as 19 Emirates Obstetrics Gynecology & Fertility Forum EOFF 2023(Postpartum Haemorrhage Workshop) .19 Emirates Obstetrics Gynecology & Fertility Forum EOFF 2024(Assisted Vaginal Delivery Team approach) 2024

Date: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the session/workshop: Parallel Workshop - 1:15 PM - 3:15 PM

Location: Saqr Ballroom B

Title: Implementing EEPAs for Workplace based assessment: A Hands-on workshop

Contributor(s):

Dr. Teodora Ucenic

Session/Workshop Details

This workshop provides concise, practical training to clinical faculty and program directors on effectively using Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs) for day-to-day trainee evaluation.

Learning Outcomes: By the end of the workshop, clinical faculty and program directors will be equipped to incorporate **EPAs into their programs, to support robust decision-making.**

Background: The EPAs are a structured method to assess clinical competencies that inform trainee promotion and eligibility for Emirati Board exit examinations. The EPAs for each specialty are developed by the **National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS) in collaboration with respective scientific committees.**

Workshop Details: During the interactive session, participants will learn how to gather, interpret, and apply EPA data using a new electronic platform set for imminent launch. Discussions will cover the approval pathway, scoring calculations, and integrating assessment outcomes into summative decisions. Hands-on exercises will help attendees practice making evidence-based judgments on trainee performance, ensuring transparency and consistency across different specialties.

Conclusion: Ultimately, this approach strengthens postgraduate medical education by maintaining high-quality standards and promoting continuous competency development for future healthcare professionals

Biography

Graduated Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Tg. Mures, Romania, (1980 – 1986).

Previous Appointments:

- 2004 – 2020: consultant Ob/Gyn in governmental and private hospitals in Al Ain and Abu Dhabi.
- 1994 – 2004: Consultant, University Hospital Sibiu, Romania.
- 1/2/1994 – 31/05/1998: Specialist, University Hospital Sibiu, Romania.
- 1/1/1991 – 31/1/1994: Resident, Ob/Gyn University Hospital No. 2 Tg. Mures, Romania.

Academic Appointments:

- 2021 – to date: Assistant professor Obs/Gyn at CMHS, UAEU, Al Ain
- 1/07/2016 - 28/2/2017: core faculty, Chair of PEC Residency Program Corniche Hospital.

- 1/1/2013 – 30/06/2015: Ob/Gyn residency program director, Al Ain Hospital.
- 1/09/2013 – 28/2/2017: adjunct Assistant Professor Ob/Gyn, CMHS Al Ain.
- 22/08/2010 – 31/12/2012: Core faculty Ob/Gyn residency program, Al Ain Hospital,
- 7/3/1996 – 01/07/2004: Assistant Professor, Faculty of Medicine Sibiu, Romania.
- 1/6/1993 – 6/3/1996: Medical researcher Ob/Gyn. Center for Public Health and Medical Researches Sibiu, branch of Romanian Academy for Medical Sciences.

Personal statement:

Using a lifelong carrier, I want to dedicate all my clinical, academic, and administrative expertise to the new generations of doctors.

I wish them to become eminent physicians, ethical, strong and reliable pillars of their society.

Research Presentations

Date of Presentation: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 2.45 PM - 2.55 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Factors Influencing Interns' Selection of Postgraduate Residency Programs in the United Arab Emirates (UAE)*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Khaled Aldahmani

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Maryam Al Dhaheri ,
- Dr. Jayadevan Sreedharan ,
- Dr. Salah Eldin Kassab,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Background

Choosing a residency program is a critical decision for medical interns, shaping their future careers. In the UAE, while past studies focused on medical students' preferences, little is known about the factors influencing interns' choices, especially with recent advances in the country's residency offerings.

Methods

Purpose & Objectives: To assess factors Influencing Interns' selection of postgraduate residency training programs in the United Arab Emirates (UAE)

Materials & Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted using online questionnaires from May to July 2024. All interns registered in the Department of Health (Abu Dhabi & Dubai) and Emirates Health Services for the 2023-2024 academic year were invited. The survey, adapted from prior studies, assessed demographics, program preferences, and key factors affecting residency choices.

Findings of Study: Out of 300 invited interns, 170 responded (56.7%). The majority were female (65.9%), and the mean age was 24 years. Interns represented 18 nationalities, with 42.4% from the UAE, 29.4% from other GCC, 17.6% from Asian countries and the remaining from other countries. The three most preferred residency choices were General Medicine (13.5%), Pediatrics (11.2%), and Emergency Medicine (11.2%). The top factors (rated as "very important"), influencing residency selection were interest in the specialty (70%), professional development opportunities (62.9%), and program reputation (51.8%). About 96% believed that program accreditation is essential for their future careers.

Conclusions: Conclusion

This study highlights the critical factors influencing interns' residency selection, providing insights for program directors to enhance residency training and align with interns' expectations.

Key Words: Internship, Factors, Residency programs

Biography

Dr. Khaled Aldahmani is a consultant endocrinologist and chairman of Academic Affairs at STMC and Tawam Hospital. He is also an Ass Professor at CMHS, UAE University

He earned his MBBS from UAE University and completed his internal medicine and endocrinology training in Canada. He also completed a fellowship in pituitary disorders and thyroid cancer.

Dr Aldahmani is a past president of the Gulf Association of Endocrinology and Diabetes(GAED), scientific chairperson of the Emirates Diabetes and endocrinology Society and a board member of the Arab Thyroid Association. He is also a chairman of the Annual Al-Ain Research Day since 2016.

Dr.Aldahmani is the DIO for Tawam and STMC.

Date of Presentation: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 2:55 PM - 3:05 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Developing a Competency-Based Residency Selection Framework: Aligning Selection Tools with ACGME Core Competencies*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Wail Bamadhaf

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Dima Abdelmanan,
- Dr. Shaza Asfari,
- Dr. Rasha Buhumaid,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The competitive and rigorous residency selection process for medical students often suffers from variability and a lack of transparency across programs. Current selection practices rely heavily on subjective elements such as interviews and recommendation letters, which may not accurately predict a resident's performance. Traditional metrics, like exam scores, have shown inconsistent correlation with successful residency outcomes, and non-technical attributes are frequently overlooked.

Purpose & Objectives: This study aims to develop a competency-based residency selection framework by aligning the selection tools employed at the Graduate Medical Education (GME) of Mohammed Bin Rashid University of Medicine and Health Sciences (MBRU) with the Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education (ACGME) core competencies. The focus is on enhancing the objectivity and comprehensiveness of the residency application review process.

Materials & Methods: Utilizing the Delphi methodology, the research engages an expert panel to assess and provide feedback on existing selection tools through multiple rounds of surveys and questionnaires. This iterative process aims to reach a consensus on the alignment of current selection practices with ACGME competencies. Data collected from these rounds will be analyzed to identify areas of agreement and convergence among experts.

Findings of Study: The study is expected to reveal significant insights into improving the residency selection process by incorporating a more holistic review that includes personality traits and situational judgment assessments. Developing a competency-based framework is anticipated to enhance the alignment of selection tools with outcome-oriented competencies, promoting a more learner-centered approach.

Conclusions: The competency-based residency selection framework developed through this study promises to provide a structured, transparent, and comprehensive approach to residency selection. By mapping selection tools to ACGME core competencies, the framework could better assess candidates' capabilities, ultimately improving residency program outcomes.

Key Words: Residency Selection, Competency-Based Education, ACGME Core Competencies.

References: John C. Burkhardt, Kendra P. Parekh, Fiona E. Gallahue, Kory S. London, Mary A. Edens, A. J. Humbert, M. Tyson Pillow, Sally A. Santen, Laura R. Hopson; A Critical Disconnect: Residency

Selection Factors Lack Correlation With Intern Performance. *J Grad Med Educ* 1 December 2020; 12(6): 696–704. doi: <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-D-20-00013.1>

Wycliffe-Jones K, Hecker KG, Schipper S, Topps M, Robinson J, Abedin T. Selection for family medicine residency training in Canada: How consistently are the same students ranked by different programs? *Can Fam Physician*. 2018 Feb;64(2):129-134. PMID: 29449245; PMCID: PMC5964389.

Biography

A Double-Board Emergency Medicine consultant, holding a master's degree in health professions education. I have been a core faculty member of the emergency medicine residency program since 2016 and was awarded the best teaching faculty by the Emirates Society of Emergency Medicine. I am appointed Deputy Designated Institutional Official for postgraduate medical education and lead the professional development section at Rashid Hospital. The most fulfilling aspect of my job is teaching, supervising, and mentoring trainees and other faculty in the clinical environment. Additionally, I strive to constantly improve the clinical education experience offered by UAE postgraduate program

Date of Presentation: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 3:15 PM - 3:25 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *The Framework of Leadership in Academic Medicine (FLAM); a mixed-methods study to develop leadership skills and competence*

Presenter's Name: Prof. Salman Yousuf Guraya

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Dr. Nihar Dash,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: In medical academic institutions, leadership is mostly hierarchical which is based on multiple factors including seniority and ranks. There is a dearth of structured leadership training, development, and certification programs in the medical field.

Purpose & Objectives: This original study contemplated to develop a framework of leadership in academic medicine with an intent to support medical academia in fostering their leadership skills.

Materials & Methods: We adopted a cross-sectional prospective design and a mixed-methods strategy. An online self-administered questionnaire-based survey and structured in-person interviews were conducted to collect the perceptions of both academic leaders and non-leaders in medicine. The data was collated, analyzed and triangulated to develop domains and themes.

Findings of Study: Of the 229 respondents, there were 121 leaders and 108 regular faculty members. The quantitative results revealed that most leaders (60%; 73/121) were open to training and development to improve their leadership skills. Leaders favored an affiliative style of leadership (45%). The leaders concurred that leadership development programs would improve their organizational performance. They also argued that an overly bureaucratic and stagnant organizational structure was a hindrance to effective leadership (mean rank scores 136.82 and 122.85 respectively). On the other hand, the majority of non-leaders (70%; 75/108) had observed that their leaders would display a variety of key leadership behaviors such as clear communication, effective resource allocation, the creation of shared knowledge and objectives. As many as 99/108 non-leaders agreed that the lack of experience and training were barriers to effective leadership. The participants recognized the need for an extensive, structured training program for academic leadership in medicine. The qualitative data analysis and triangulation of subthemes helped us to develop the 6 Es Framework for Leadership in Academic Medicine (FLAM); Ethics (accountability, role model, respect), Education and training (training programs, structured curriculum), Envision (clear path, talent hunting, team man), Engagement (structural foundation, achievable targets), Empowerment (employees, create passion), and Encouragement (financial rewards).

Conclusions: Our study underpins the need for a structured training program of leadership in academic medicine. The 6Es FLAM, with its distinct traits, can be incorporated into undergraduate and postgraduate medical curriculum to enhance the impact of leadership in academic medicine.

Key Words: Leadership; Framework; Academia; Ethics; Empowerment

References: - Khoshhal KI, Guraya SY. Leaders produce leaders and managers produce followers: a systematic review of the desired competencies and standard settings for physicians' leadership. Saudi medical journal. 2016;37(10):1061.

- Buckner KG, McDowelle JO. Developing teacher leaders: Providing encouragement, opportunities, and support. NASSP bulletin. 2000;84(616):35-41.

- Carvalho T, Diogo S. Women rectors and leadership narratives: the same male norm? Education Sciences. 2018;8(2):75.

Biography

Prof. Salman Guraya is currently serving as Professor of Surgery at the University of Sharjah UAE. He is a qualified medical educator, researcher, and minimally invasive surgeon He is a senior editor of BMC Med Educ, Frontiers in Surg Oncol, and Advancesin Biomedical and Health Journals.

Prof. Guraya was awarded Int'l Research Award of World Top 2% Scientists by Stanford University and the TAGHEER Award for Strategic Performance. He is an examiner of RCS Ireland and for the Fellowship in European Board of Surgery and a faculty of the Colorectal and Transanal Surgery program by IRCAD in Strasbourg France. Prof. Guraya has several national and Int'l leadership roles in academics, UG/PG clinical training, assessment, accreditation, research, and branding. He is a Regional Conveyor for Blended Learning UK, co-Director of MSc. Coloproctology by University of East Anglia UK, Director of BSS/CCrISP courses by RCS UK, and global medical professionalism network, RCS Ireland. Prof. Guraya has published extensively in world premier journals with around 150 co-researchers from UAE, UK, Germany, France, Malaysia, Italy, KSA and Pakistan. In surgery, his main areas of research include surgical oncology, colorectal surgery, transaoral scar-less surgery, and in medical education, medical professionalism, interprofessional collaboration, and academic leadership.

Date of Presentation: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 3:25 PM - 3:35 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Assessing burnout syndrome and its predictors in postgraduate residents in United Arab Emirates*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Adnan Agha

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Mohammed Al Houqani,
- Dr. Muhammad Jawad Hashim,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Burnout is a mental condition defined as a result of continuous and long-term stress exposure, particularly related to psychosocial, interpersonal and environmental stressors, and is defined by 3 classical dimensions – emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and lack of personal accomplishment. Extensive clinical training over many years and irregular shift-work hours, high levels of responsibility of patients health and safety can contribute to factors leading to high burnout in doctors especially postgraduate medical residents which is generally at higher level than in the normal working population, which can cause poor work engagement and wellbeing.

Purpose & Objectives: The purpose of this study is to estimate the prevalence of burnout syndrome in training resident doctors by using Oldenburg Burnout inventory in United Arab Emirates National institute of Health Sciences accredited medical training programs.

Materials & Methods: This was a cross-sectional analytical study using National institute of Health Sciences (NIHS) platform to invite postgraduate resident trainees who are in the program for at least 6 months to fill a questionnaire as part of their annual survey after informed consent. Residents who self-reported presence of past psychiatric illness or taking treatment were excluded. This survey contained demographics, work patterns, possible predictors of work related stress and Oldenburg burnout inventory. All this information was collected through a specially designed online proforma which will be on an online secure platform. The data collected was analyzed by SPSS package for Microsoft Windows version 22.0

Findings of Study: Over 600 physicians/interns/residents in NIHS training programs participated in this burnout study. Burnout found to be high among postgraduate residents in United Arab Emirates. The commonest factor that predicted resident physician burnout seems to be increased presence of breaking the specified rule that states that "duty hours must be limited to 80 per week, averaged over a four-week period, inclusive of all in-house call activities?". The

Conclusions: Burnout is common in postgraduate residents in NIHS training programs across various specialties and regions with various predictors identified in this study. Since burnout syndrome is reversible condition and appropriate organizational strategies and positive engagement and work adaptation should be encouraged to

Key Words: burnout syndrome, postgraduate residents, doctor burnout

- References:** 1. Maslach C, Jackson SE, Leiter MP. Maslach burnout inventory manual. 4th Edition. Palo Alto, CA: Consulting Psychologists Press; 2016
2. Melamed S, Shirom A, Toker S, Berliner S, Shapira: Burnout and risk of cardiovascular disease: evidence, possible causal paths, and promising research directions. *Psychol Bull* 2006, 132:327-53.
3. Dyrbye L, Shanafelt T. A narrative review on burnout experienced by medical students and residents. *Med Educ*. 2016 Jan;50(1):132-49.
4. Ishak W, Nikraves R, Lederer S, Perry R, Ogunyemi D, Bernstein C. Burnout in medical students: a systematic review. *Clin Teach*. 2013 Aug;10(4):242-5.
5. Abdulrahman M, Nair SC, Farooq MM, Al Kharmiri A, Al Marzooqi F, Carrick FR. Burnout and depression among medical residents in the United Arab Emirates: A Multicenter study. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2018 Mar-Apr;7(2):435-441.
6. Janssen N, Kant IJ, Swaen GM, Janssen PPM, Schroer CAP: Fatigue as a predictor of sickness absence: results from the Maastricht cohort study on fatigue at work. *Occup Environ Med* 2003, 60:71–6.
7. Agha A, Basu A, Hanif W. Burnout in diabetes and endocrinology specialist registrars across England, Scotland and Wales in the pre-COVID era. *Prim Care Diabetes*. 2022; 3: S1751-9918
8. Gundersen L. Physician burnout. *Ann Int Med*. 2001; 4: 145-48.
9. Smith R: Why are doctors so unhappy? *Brit Med J* 2001, 322:1073-1074.
10. Demerouti, E., A. B. Bakker, F. Nachreiner, and W. B. Schaufeli. 2001. The Job Demands-resources Model of Burnout. *Journal of Applied Psychology* 86: 499.

Biography

Dr. Muhammad Jawad Hashim

I am an Assistant Professor Internal Medicine at CMHS UAEU and
Consultant Diabetes & Endocrinology, Tawam Hospital,

My passion is improving care and overall experience of my patients by developing exceptional service that provides highest standards of excellence for clinical care and maximizes efficiency using Kata principles of engagement/improvement/ leadership.

My interests include improving access and delivery of Diabetes health care; Psychology & Technology in Type 1 diabetes, improving clinical reasoning in medical education and assessing burnout in healthcare professionals.

I have FRCP (Fellow of Royal College of Physicians) of London, Dual CCT in General Internal Medicine and Diabetes & Endocrinology. Other Medical qualifications include MRCP Diabetes & Endocrinology; MRCPUK, FCPS Internal Medicine and MCPS Internal Medicine

Date of Presentation: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 3:45 PM - 3:55 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Perception of OSCE as an Assessment Tool in Undergraduate Medical Students Insights from Dubai Medical College for Girls*

Presenter's Name: Dr. YASSEIN KAMAL ALHAJ ELHUSSEIN

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Nadia ElRouby
- Dr. Hiba R A Mohamed

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Objective Structured Clinical Examination (OSCE) is globally recognized as a valid and reliable tool for assessing clinical competencies in medical education. However, understanding the perceptions of students towards OSCE is essential for improving its effectiveness. This study investigates the perceptions of fourth-year undergraduate medical students at Dubai Medical College for Girls towards OSCE in their final Obstetrics & Gynecology and Pediatrics examinations.

Purpose & Objectives: The primary objective of this research is to evaluate students' attitudes and preferences toward OSCE, identify factors influencing their perceptions, and assess the impact of OSCE on their learning experiences. The findings will help improve the OSCE design and implementation at the institution.

Materials & Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among 50 fourth-year medical students at Dubai Medical College for Girls. An electronic questionnaire was distributed after the completion of OSCE in both Obstetrics & Gynecology and Pediatrics rotations. The survey covered various aspects of the examination, including station organization, time management, feedback mechanisms, and overall satisfaction with the assessment tool. Data were analyzed using SPSS to generate descriptive statistics.

Findings of Study: Preliminary analysis revealed that 70% of students agreed or strongly agreed that the sequence of stations was comfortable, and 60% found the time allocated for each station to be sufficient. However, 20% of students expressed concerns about the clarity of the exam process before starting. Overall, 65% agreed that OSCE minimized the chances of failing and was a fair assessment tool. Key concerns raised included insufficient time at some stations and the need for more constructive feedback.

Conclusions: The majority of students perceived OSCE as a fair and useful assessment tool in medical education. However, specific improvements, particularly regarding time allocation and feedback mechanisms, could enhance the overall student experience and the effectiveness of the assessment. The findings suggest that refining OSCE to better align with students' needs could contribute to improved learning outcomes and clinical readiness.

Key Words: OSCE, student perception, assessment tool

References: 1. Harden M, et al. Assessment of clinical competence using objective structured examination. Br Med J. 1975.

2. Nasir AA, et al. Medical students' perception of OSCE: A feedback for process improvement. JSE. 2014.

Biography

Yassein Elhussein, MBBS, is an ECFMG-certified Doctor passionate about Internal Medicine, community health, and medical education. He earned his degree from University of Gezira Faculty of Medicine, Sudan, and has since demonstrated excellence in both clinical practice and research.

Dr. Elhussein has a distinguished academic record and received several awards. Driven by a deep interest in Internal Medicine and a commitment to lifelong learning, Dr. Elhussein has contributed to numerous healthcare initiatives in both resource-limited settings and modern academic institutions. He is particularly noted for his contributions to medical education since his time as a medical student.

Dr. Elhussein is passionate about teaching and mentoring, currently serving as a Clinical Tutor at Dubai Medical University, where he helps shape the next generation of healthcare professionals. His love for education and research is evident in his involvement in various projects and activities.

Outside of medicine, Dr. Elhussein enjoys sketching portraits and performing magic tricks, reflecting his appreciation for detail, creativity, and communication, skills that also define his medical practice.

Dr. Elhussein is preparing to pursue a residency in Internal Medicine in the United States, where he aims to further his expertise and contribute to healthcare delivery in diverse, dynamic environments.

Date of Presentation: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 4:05 PM - 4:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Implementing a Training Program to enhance the Competency of Clinical Mentors in Cardiac Catheterization Laboratory*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Noof mohamed althawadi

Co-Authors:

- -

Abstract

Background & Introduction: In healthcare, clinical mentors are crucial stakeholders who support mentees' learning processes. However, some mentors could be unconfident or may lack the necessary mentoring competencies. Hence, it is essential to ensure sufficient clinical mentoring education. The current evidence indicates a lack of mentoring education and the need for clinical mentoring competency improvement.

Purpose & Objectives: The aim of the organization development project was to implement a mentoring training program in the cardiac catheterization laboratory to improve the competency and confidence of clinical mentors.

Materials & Methods: To ensure successful implementation, the Health Service Executive (HSE) model was employed to lead the project's change process. Additionally, the Context/Input/Process/Product (CIPP) model was employed to evaluate the project's achievements. The evaluation included a mixed-methods approach of a pre-intervention questionnaire, a post-intervention questionnaire, and interviews. The responses to the questionnaires were statistically analyzed, while the thematic analysis method was used to analyze the interview data.

Findings of Study: A total of 24 clinical mentors participated in the questionnaires, while five were interviewed. The findings indicate an improvement in clinical mentors' competency (31%) and confidence (27.7%); those findings were reflected in three themes: mentoring competency, mentoring confidence, and stakeholder involvement.

Conclusions: The outcome of the project reflects the successful implementation of the mentoring training program. Those findings could be beneficial for developing, planning, and implementing a mentoring training for all healthcare professionals. The study recommended a mandatory mentoring training program for all clinical mentors as a requirement for mentoring students

Key Words: clinical mentoring, clinical mentors, mentoring education

References: Feyissa, G., Balabanova, D., & Woldie, M. (2019). How Effective are Mentoring Programs for Improving Health Worker Competence and Institutional Performance in Africa? A Systematic Review of Quantitative Evidence. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, 12, 989-1005. <https://doi.org/10.2147/jmdh.s228951>

Tuomikoski, A. M., Ruotsalainen, H., Mikkonen, K., Miettunen, J., Juvonen, S., Sivonen, P., & Kääriäinen, M. (2020). How mentoring education affects nurse mentors' competence in mentoring students during clinical practice – a quasi-experimental study.' *Scandinavian Journal of Caring Sciences*, 34(1), 230–238. <https://doi.org/10.1111/scs.12728>

Biography

I am Noof Mohamed Althawadi, a healthcare professional from Bahrain with an outstanding academic and professional background. I hold a Bachelor's degree in Medical Diagnostic Imaging from the University of Sharjah in the United Arab Emirates, where I graduated with the highest honors.

Driven to further my education, I went on to earn a Master of Science (MSc) degree in Leadership in Health Profession Education from the University of Sharjah, UAE, in collaboration with the University of East Anglia in the United Kingdom. Again, I graduated with the highest honors.

Currently, I am pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Health Professions Education at the University of Maastricht in the Netherlands, demonstrating my relentless pursuit of knowledge and skills in the healthcare field.

Since 2021, I have been working as an educator and radiographer at the Mohammed bin Khalifa Cardiac Center in Bahrain, where I continue to contribute to the medical community. My research interests focus on enhancing the competency clinical mentors and evaluating the effectiveness of continuous medical education delivery. I have presented my research at conferences such as the UAEGSRC 2023 and the TUFH 2023 conference, and have published one research paper with others in progress.

Date of Presentation: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 4:15 PM - 4:25 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Mentorship Pilot Program in Graduate Medical Education*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Hira Salman

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Dima Kamal Abdelmannan,
- Dr. Jaidev Raghu Nath ,
- Dr. , Oghowan Abdelrahman Osman Bashir,
- Dr. Rasha Bhumaid,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Mentorship plays a vital role in Graduate Medical Education (GME), providing numerous benefits that enhance both the professional and personal development of trainees. The Mentorship Pilot Program was launched within the Internal Medicine and Pediatrics residency programs.

Purpose & Objectives: The primary objective of the pilot program is to develop a structured mentorship framework for all GME programs.

Materials & Methods: The program involved strategic planning sessions, stakeholder meetings, and benchmarking with international experts. A faculty survey was conducted to gauge interest and gather input on preferred mentoring formats. The program includes training materials, meeting logs, and a standardized approach to mentorship with clear objectives, confidentiality protocols, and evaluation criteria.

Findings of Study: A total of 1,444 GME clinical faculty across all specialties were surveyed, and 547 (37.8%) expressed interest in mentorship. 45% of the faculty in the internal medicine and pediatric programs expressed interest in participating in the mentorship pilot program.

34% of the residents expressed interest in participating in the mentorship pilot program. A total of 42 mentors and mentees were successfully matched based on preferences.

Conclusions: Preliminary findings indicate a notable interest among faculty and trainees in participating in the mentorship pilot program, with higher interest shown by faculty compared to trainees. The program will be evaluated upon completion of the pilot, focusing on identifying strategies to enhance engagement among both faculty and trainees. The program aims to promote professional growth and collaboration and has the potential to be scaled up at the academic healthcare system level within Dubai Health.

Key Words: GME, Mentorship, Mentees, Mentors, Faculty Development

References: Khan, N. R., Rialon, K. L., Buretta, K. J., Deslauriers, J. R., Harwood, J. L., & Jardine, D. A. (2017). Residents as mentors: the development of resident mentorship milestones.

Ramanan, R. A., Taylor, W. C., Davis, R. B., & Phillips, R. S. (2006). Mentoring matters: mentoring and career preparation in internal medicine residency training. *Journal of general internal medicine*, 21(4), 340-345.

McKenna, A. M., & Straus, S. E. (2011). Charting a professional course: a review of mentorship in medicine. *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 8(2), 109-112.

Biography

I am a DHA-licensed GP with significant clinical experience in OBS/GYN, including recent involvement in telemedicine initiatives. Currently, I serve a team of Graduate medical experts who are dedicated to transforming and contributing to the establishment of Dubai academic health systems.

My research interests are focused on advancing medical education and I am deeply committed to leveraging the power of technology to enhance the quality and accessibility of medical education. I am enthusiastic about using innovative tools and platforms to promote personal and professional development.

I am highly motivated to develop my skills and knowledge in telemedicine, as I believe it offers significant potential for improving healthcare outcomes and enhancing patient access to medical services. As such, I am constantly exploring new opportunities to expand my expertise in this area and apply it to the benefit of patients and healthcare professionals alike.

Date of Presentation: 15 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 4:25 PM - 4:35 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Evaluating the Effectiveness of Item-Writing Workshops on the Quality of Items for Oman Medical Specialty Board Examinations (OMSB)*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Ibtihal Salim Saud Al Mandhari

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Dr. Abdullah Rashid Al Battashi,
- Dr. Iman Mohammed Al Lawati ,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: High-quality examinations are essential in medical education to ensure valid and reliable evaluations of learners and to effectively assess the professional competence of healthcare professionals/ residents/ specialists. Developing well-structured multiple-choice questions (MCQs) requires specialized training for item writers across medical specialties. This study examines the impact of an item-writing workshop on improving the quality of MCQs developed by SMEs from various disciplines at the Oman Medical Specialty Board (OMSB), including Family Medicine, Anesthesia, Emergency Medicine, Orthopedic Surgery, Radiology, Otolaryngology, and Psychiatry.

Purpose & Objectives: The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of Item Constructing workshop on the quality of MCQ items developed by Item Writers from various Medical Specialties.

Materials & Methods: A structured item-writing workshop was delivered to SMEs to enhance their item-writing skills and align their item development with OMSB guidelines. A mixed-methods approach was employed, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative analyses. A total of 20 MCQs were assessed before and after the workshop using a structured item-writing checklist. A paired t-test was conducted to compare item quality across key components, such as item stems, lead-in clarity, and option plausibility. Additionally, an online survey was distributed to assess participant confidence and perceptions of the workshop's effectiveness.

Findings of Study: The analysis revealed statistically significant improvements in MCQ quality, with notable enhancements in lead-in clarity, plausibility of answer choices, and linguistic precision ($p < 0.001$). SMEs with limited prior experience in item construction demonstrated the most significant gains, contributing to greater standardization of item quality across specialties. Survey feedback indicated a marked increase in participants' confidence (100%) in writing high-quality assessment items.

Conclusions: The findings confirm that structured item-writing workshops significantly enhance MCQ quality in medical assessments. By equipping SMEs with the necessary skills, such training contributes to fairer and more reliable evaluations. Future research could explore the long-term sustainability of these improvements and the potential for integrating periodic refresher workshops into faculty development programs.

Key Words: Medical education Item-writing workshops Multiple-choice questions (MCQs) Assessment quality Oman Medical Specialty Board (OMSB) Faculty development Validity and reliability Healthcare professionals Educational assessment Standardization Quantitative anal

References: Tarrant, M., & Ware, J. (2023). Construction and Writing Flaws of the Multiple-Choice Questions in Medical Education: A Systematic Review. *Journal of Medical Education and Curricular Development*, 10, 238212052311552. <https://doi.org/10.1177/238212052311552>

Biography

My name is Ibtihal Al Mandhari, and I am a written examination specialist at the Oman Medical Specialty Board (OMSB), with over two and a half years of experience in developing and ensuring the quality of assessments for medical specialties such as anesthesia and internal medicine and medical microbiology. My role involves aligning examinations with international standards to support the professional development of healthcare practitioners in Oman.

I hold a Bachelor of Health Science and a Master of Podiatric Practice from La Trobe University in Melbourne, Australia. My academic and professional experiences have equipped me with a deep understanding of effective assessment methodologies and their role in advancing medical education.

I am committed to contributing to the continuous improvement of healthcare education through collaboration, innovation, and adherence to best practices. I look forward to participating in this conference to exchange knowledge and enhance my contributions to the field of medical education.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:15 PM - 1:25 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *EPA Pilot in Medical Internship Program*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Ayesha Saeed Almheiri

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Rasha Bhumaid ,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The transition from medical education to clinical practice is a critical phase requiring competent and confident practitioners. Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs) have emerged as a key strategy in competency-based medical education, bridging the gap between theory and practice and is assessment requirement for the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS).

Purpose & Objectives: The primary objective of this pilot study was to integrate EPAs into a medical internship program to enhance the assessment of clinical competencies. We aimed to evaluate the perceptions of trainees and trainers implementing EPAs in the internship curriculum.

Materials & Methods: The pilot was conducted over a 8 weeks period in a academic healthcare system hospitals with 80 medical interns. The NIHS EPAs were integrated into daily clinical activities across various rotations, including internal medicine, pediatrics, and family medicine. Interns were assessed on NIHS EPAs relevant to each rotation using direct observations and feedback from supervisors. Post pilot, surveys/interviews were implemented to gauge intern and faculty experiences.

Findings of Study: Preliminary results suggest high levels of satisfaction among both interns and supervising faculty, highlighting the clarity, and relevance EPA-based assessments. Faculty suggested minor edits to improve the practicality of implementation. The findings suggest that EPAs represent a valuable framework for competency-based evaluations in clinical settings, encouraging more precise, actionable feedback and skill development.

Conclusions: The pilot implementation of EPAs in a medical internship program appears to be a feasible and effective method for enhancing competency-based education. The positive outcomes underscore the potential for EPAs to be scaled and adapted in various medical training contexts. Future research should focus on longitudinal impacts on clinical performance and patient care outcomes.

Key Words: Entrustable Professional Activities, Medical Internship.

References: Obeso V, Grbic D, Emery M, et al. Core Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs) and the Transition from Medical School to Residency: the Postgraduate Year One Resident Perspective. *Med Sci Educ.* 2021;31(6):1813-1822. Published 2021 Sep 10. doi:10.1007/s40670-021-01370-3

Eliasz KL, Nick MW, Zabar S, et al. Viewing Readiness-for-Residency through Binoculars: Mapping Competency-Based Assessments to the AAMC's 13 Core Entrustable Professional Activities (EPAs). *Teach Learn Med.* 2023;35(4):436-441. doi:10.1080/10401334.2022.2082432

Biography

Dr. Ayesha AlMheiri is a dedicated Family Medicine Specialist, Medical Internship Program Director, and Chair of training at Dubai Health. She earned her Arab Board and MRCGP certifications in Family Medicine in 2021, a foundation that has fueled her commitment to both clinical practice and medical education. Her passion for teaching led her to complete a degree in Leadership in Health Profession Education in 2020, a milestone that shaped her philosophy around learner-centered education.

As an educator, Dr. AlMheiri integrates active learning methods like Team-Based Learning (TBL), Case-Based Learning (CBL), and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) into her teaching. Her journey began as a Clinical Lecturer at MBRU, where she guided students through interactive TBL sessions. In 2021, she became a core faculty member in the Family Medicine residency, redesigning educational activities to foster self-directed learning and critical thinking.

Since her appointment as Medical Internship Program Director in 2023, Dr. AlMheiri has ensured trainees receive exceptional training across multiple clinical sites, emphasizing mentorship and high-quality assessments.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:25 PM - 1:35 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *ROLE OF AI TOOLS IN ENHANCING THE EDUCATIONAL AND PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROCESSES IN PHARMACY EDUCATION*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Rasha Saad Suliman

Co-Authors:

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Abstract

Background & Introduction: Professional identity formation (PIF) is a dynamic process integral to the development of pharmacy students and residents as healthcare practitioners. This article presents a schematic representation and guide for medical educators to navigate the complexities of PIF and socialization in pharmacy education. The schematic outlines key phases, including pre-professional, academic, transition, professional, and leadership stages, each influenced by factors such as personal attributes, educational experiences, and role modeling (Adams, et al. 2006).

Purpose & Objectives: To present a schematic representation and guide for medical educators to navigate the complexities of PIF and socialization in pharmacy education.

Materials & Methods: The schematic outlines key phases of PIF, including pre-professional, academic, transition, professional, and leadership stages. Each phase is influenced by factors such as personal attributes, educational experiences, and role modeling. The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) tools is also explored as a means to enhance the PIF process.

Findings of Study: Key Phases and Influences:

- Pre-professional Stage: Influenced by personal attributes and initial interest in pharmacy.
- Academic Stage: Shaped by educational experiences and academic curriculum.
- Transition Stage: Marked by experiential learning opportunities and real-world applications.
- Professional Stage: Characterized by role modeling and mentorship.
- Leadership Stage: Focuses on interprofessional education and lifelong learning.

AI Integration:

- AI-driven Analytics: Helps track student progress, identify areas needing improvement, and tailor educational experiences.
- AI-based Simulations: Provides realistic, interactive scenarios for experiential learning.
- AI-powered Mentoring Platforms: Facilitates effective and personalized mentorship.

Conclusions: Recommendations:

Medical educators should:

1. Create supportive environments.
2. Provide experiential learning opportunities.
3. Facilitate mentorship and role modeling.
4. Promote interprofessional education.
5. Encourage lifelong learning.
6. Integrate AI tools to enhance PIF.

Conclusion:

By understanding and actively engaging in the PIF process, and leveraging AI tools, educators can effectively guide pharmacy learners towards becoming competent, compassionate, and professional practitioners dedicated to optimal patient care

Key Words: Professional Identity Formation (PIF), Pharmacy Education, Experiential Learning, Mentorship, Role Modeling, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and Healthcare Practitioners

References: References

Adams, K., Hean, S., Sturgis, P., and Clark, J.M. (2006) 'Investigating the Factors Influencing Professional Identity of First-year Health and Social Care Students'. *Learning in Health and Social Care* 5 (2), 55–68

Gooding, H.C., Mann, K., and Armstrong, E. (2017) 'Twelve Tips for Applying the Science of Learning to Health Professions Education'. *Medical Teacher* 39 (1), 26–31

Biography

Dr. Rasha Saad Suliman is an esteemed Associate Professor of Pharmaceutical Sciences at Fatima College of Health Sciences, Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates. She holds a Bachelor's degree from the University of Khartoum, Sudan (2004), and a Ph.D. in Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences from the University of Technology Malaysia (UiTM) (2013). In 2025, she furthered her education with a Master's degree in Medical Education from Warwick University, UK, complementing her MBA from UniRazak, Malaysia (2010).

In 2019, she was appointed Associate Professor at King Saud University for Health Sciences (KSAU-HS), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia.

A licensed Pharmacy Consultant at the Sudan Medical Council, Dr. Rasha is also a certified quality reviewer by the NCAAA, Saudi Arabia's quality assurance body, and a member of The Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education in the UK. Currently, she chairs the Curriculum and Quality Assurance Committees and co-chairs the International Accreditation ACPE Steering Committees.

Dr. Rasha is a distinguished research scholar with an H-index of 15 and an i10-index of 17 on Google Scholar. She has authored over 100 original research articles in high-impact journals, focusing on drug discovery, design, and development.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:35 PM - 1:45 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Student and Faculty Perception of AI Integration in Educational Policies and Procedures: A Reflection on the Experience of Dubai Medical University*

Presenter's Name: Prof. Samar Ahmed

Co-Authors:

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Abstract

Background & Introduction: As Artificial Intelligence (AI) becomes increasingly integrated into educational institutions, its potential to revolutionize medical education is of particular interest. Dubai Medical University (DMU) has begun adopting AI-driven technologies to enhance both academic and administrative procedures. Understanding the perceptions of students and faculty in this context is crucial to ensure successful implementation and address any concerns related to AI's role in medical education. While AI offers benefits such as personalized learning and efficiency, challenges regarding ethical considerations, data privacy, and the displacement of traditional educational roles remain pertinent.

Purpose & Objectives: This study aims to:

1. Explore the perceptions of students and faculty at Dubai Medical University regarding AI integration in educational policies and procedures.
2. Investigate perceived benefits, challenges, and ethical concerns specific to a medical education setting.
3. Identify how perceptions vary between students and faculty based on academic standing and experience with AI.

Materials & Methods: The study was conducted at Dubai Medical University using a cross-sectional design. Surveys were distributed to 300 medical students and 100 faculty members, followed by in-depth interviews with 15 faculty members and 20 students. The survey assessed attitudes towards AI's role in educational processes such as personalized learning, administrative automation, and ethical concerns. Interviews provided qualitative insights, revealing deeper perceptions and concerns specific to medical education. Quantitative data were analyzed using statistical software, and thematic analysis was applied to qualitative data to capture key themes and trends.

Findings of Study: Initial findings suggest that a majority of students at DMU perceive AI as beneficial for enhancing personalized learning and improving access to medical knowledge. They also appreciate AI's role in administrative efficiency, particularly in managing schedules and assessments. Faculty, however, expressed more varied views, with concerns centering around ethical issues, particularly in the use of AI for assessments, potential bias in algorithms, and the risk of diminishing the importance of human-centered medical education. Some faculty members were also apprehensive about their evolving roles in an AI-enhanced educational landscape.

Conclusions: The experience at Dubai Medical University highlights a significant divide between students' optimism and faculty members' caution regarding AI integration in medical education. While students generally embrace AI for its potential to enhance learning, faculty concerns emphasize the need for ethical safeguards and clear policy frameworks. Addressing these concerns will be essential for the successful and responsible integration of AI into medical education at DMU.

Key Words: Artificial Intelligence, Medical Education, Policy, Faculty Perception, Student Perception, Dubai Medical University

References: 1. Luckin, R. (2017). *Towards Artificial Intelligence-Based Assessment Systems*. Springer.
2. Topol, E. (2019). *Deep Medicine: How Artificial Intelligence Can Make Healthcare Human Again*. Basic Books.

Biography

Samar is the associate Dean academic Affairs at Dubai medical college for girls, she is an educator with a track record of achievement in organizational change and curriculum development. She is the founder of the Regional FAIMER institute in the Middle East and North Africa and a holder of many education fellowships including the Karloniska Institute prize for research in Medical education fellowship.

Samar has a broad expertise in competency based education and in educational management.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:45 PM - 1:55 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Shifting an Internship Program to an NIHS-Accredited Program: The Local Experience in Al Ain Region*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Amel Alameeri

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Shamma Almuhairi,
- Dr. Moza Aldarmaki,
- Dr. Jawaher Alahbabi,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The internship program at Tawam and STMC hospitals have a long-standing history of training future healthcare professionals. In 2023, the vision for this program evolved, striving to align with higher standards by achieving accreditation from the National Institute for Health Specialties (NIHS). This milestone marked the first NIHS-accredited internship program within the emirate of Abu Dhabi.

Purpose & Objectives: To meet accreditation requirements, a comprehensive restructuring of the program was undertaken.

Materials & Methods: Key changes included the development of a new training framework, the revision of protocols for education, assessment, and evaluation, as well as the integration of research requirements

Findings of Study: These enhancements aimed to elevate the quality of internship training, ensuring alignment with NIHS standards and fostering a culture of excellence in clinical education.

Conclusions: This abstract highlight the challenges and achievements encountered during the transition and reflects on the implications for internship training in our center. The experience serves as a model for other institutions aspiring to meet similar accreditation standards while maintaining a strong focus on local needs and global best practices.

Key Words: Internship program, NIHS

References: -

Biography

Dr. Amal Eissa Mohammed Murad Abdallah Al-Ameeri, MD, MRCP (UK), Arab Board IM, FRCPI-CF/Bronchiectasis Fellowship

Dr. Amal Al-Ameeri is a distinguished consultant pulmonologist at Tawam Hospital, renowned for her expertise in cystic fibrosis and bronchiectasis. With an impressive array of credentials, including

membership in the European Cystic Fibrosis Society and the European Respiratory Society, Dr. Amal has dedicated her career to advancing respiratory medicine.

Dr. Amal's journey in medicine began at the University of Sharjah, where she earned her medical degree. Following this, she completed her residency in internal medicine at Tawam Hospital, solidifying her foundational skills and knowledge. Driven by a passion for respiratory health, she pursued a clinical fellowship in general respiratory medicine at the Royal College of Physicians of Ireland. She then received specialized training in cystic fibrosis and bronchiectasis, areas in which she has since made significant contributions.

She is a member of Advance CF group in ECSF 2024.

As the program director of the internship program at Tawam Hospital, Dr. Amal plays a pivotal role in mentoring the next generation of medical professionals. Her commitment to education and excellence in clinical practice has made her a respected leader in her field.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:55 PM - 2:05 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Contextual Surprise Theory in Postgraduate Training and Assessment*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Dixon Thomas

Co-Authors:

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Abstract

Background & Introduction: Pharmacy graduates were not showing practice readiness when they graduated. Within the undergraduate program, experiential education was added to introduce practice experience between the program, and more extensive training was included towards the end of the program. Still, practice readiness remains a concern. Those graduates who undergo postgraduate training like internship, residency, or fellowship also have some, but relatively less, practice readiness. New employees also experience issues in practice readiness that might extend from one to six months or even more for some of them. It is important to understand the core elements essentially contributing to practice readiness.

Purpose & Objectives: The purpose of this research was to create a framework that could explain the theoretical basis for concerns about practice readiness in postgraduate training. Understanding those concerns could mitigate the issue of practice readiness for postgraduate trainees more effectively. This research follows a constructivist paradigm and uses research questions rather than objectives. The research questions are as follows;

1. What elements of practice readiness are observed in a practice-ready pharmacy practitioner?
2. How could the gaps in postgraduate trainees' practice readiness be addressed in their learning and assessment?

Materials & Methods: This research uses a constructivist research paradigm and qualitative research methods. The methods include non-participant direct observation and in-depth semi-structured interviews of post-graduate trainees and their trainers. Multiple methods involving research participants different backgrounds were exercised for triangulation and validating the findings. Samples were included until no new themes were constructed and the codes fairly dense the themes. The researcher has an inside-outsider positionality, being a dispassionate observer with good access to the research site. Thematic analysis was used to interpret the data, assigning codes and themes in Atlas.ti software version 24 for Mac.

Findings of Study: The main theme co-constructed was the interconnection of a trainee within the system. Exposure to a new system in a new role at a new site, even for an experienced practitioner, adds an element of surprise that shall be resolved by sensing how the system works. Preparation is the next theme: understanding the system and knowing it works. The last theme is negotiation, like in communities of practice, theory to practice.

Conclusions: This research proposes Contextual Surprise Theory as a sub-theory to Communities of Practice. Understanding and managing contextual surprise as early as possible will help trainees prepare and negotiate their interventions contextually appropriate. Such authentic training will also help trainees develop their patterns of work and become experts at the site. Until then, the assessment expectations need to be tailored to be fair to the trainee. Contextual Surprise is more of a concept that needs to be expanded as a theory.

Key Words: Contextual, Postgraduate, Training, Assessment

References: Etienne Wenger-Trayner, Mark Fenton O’Creevy, Steven Hutchinson, Chris Kubiak, Beverly Wenger-Trayner. Learning in landscapes of practice. Routledge, 2014.

Thomas D. Clinical pharmacy education, practice and research: clinical pharmacy, drug information, pharmacovigilance, pharmacoeconomics and clinical research. Elsevier; 2018.

Biography

I am a pharmacist academician by profession. I am also building my medical education profile. I have an MS in Education Management, a Graduate Diploma in Health Professions Education, and am currently pursuing my Doctor of Education. I am working as a Professor and Associate Dean-Clinical, responsible for experiential education at Gulf Medical University College of Pharmacy. I practice as Director of Drug Information Service at Thumbay University Hospital, the campus hospital of Gulf Medical University. The presentation is part of my EdD research.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 2:05 PM - 2:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Drivers for Engagement of Health Professions Education Students in Technology-Enhanced Learning Environments*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Salah Eldin

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Hossam Hamdy,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Technology plays an important role in supporting the learning process of health professions education (HPE) students through different tools such as simulations, virtual patients, gamification, audience response systems and social media. Since student engagement is one of the predictors of academic success and well-being of students, understanding the engagement of HPE students in technology-enhanced learning (TEL) is essential. Despite the growing interest in this field, literature reviews about the drivers for student engagement in TEL are lacking from the existing HPE literature.

Purpose & Objectives: Therefore, this systematic review aims to add to the understanding about the drivers of HPE students' engagement in TEL environments

Materials & Methods: The authors searched MEDLINE, PubMed, SCOPUS, ERIC, and EBESCO for English articles published from 2000 until November 2024. In addition, we hand-searched key journals in HPE about the drivers of student engagement in TEL. Using specific selection criteria, the two authors independently reviewed the articles for eligibility, followed by data extraction using both quantitative and qualitative analysis.

Findings of Study: Of the 851 retrieved articles, 48 studies were selected for review and around 50% of them have been published in the past 3 years. Approximately 60% of the studies used quantitative approach with 50% using self-reports. The review identifies several factors driving student engagement in technology-enhanced learning (TEL) environments, emphasizing technological, teacher, student, and relational aspects. Tools like social media, microblogs, simulations, and adaptive tutorials significantly enhance cognitive, behavioral, and emotional engagement, while teacher practices such as techno-pedagogical skills and instructional prompts further promote engagement, albeit with a potential reduction in social presence in online settings. Student-related factors, including self-concept, learning satisfaction, and peer-assisted learning, also play a critical role in fostering engagement.

Conclusions: The review highlights several key factors influencing student engagement in technology-enhanced learning (TEL) environments, with a focus on technological, teacher, student, and relational elements. Gaps exist in understanding the long-term impact on knowledge retention, skill transfer, and the role of social presence in online learning. Future research should focus on longitudinal studies and strategies to enhance emotional engagement and address the social dimensions of TEL.

Key Words: Student engagement, technology-enhanced learning, health professions education

References: KASSAB, S. E., TAYLOR, D. & HAMDY, H. 2023. Student engagement in health professions education: AMEE Guide No. 152. *Med Teach*, 45, 949-965.

BALALLE, H. 2024. Exploring student engagement in technology-based education in relation to gamification, online/distance learning, and other factors: A systematic literature review. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 9.

Biography

Prof. Kassab is a Professor of Physiology and Medical Education, and Associate Dean Academics at the College of Medicine, Gulf Medical University. He was the Associate Dean for Academic Affairs, CMED, Qatar University and Vice Dean for Academic Affairs at Arabian Gulf University.

Prof. Kassab holds a PhD degree in Medical Education from Erasmus University Rotterdam in addition to his PhD in medical Physiology. He worked as a post-doctoral fellow and then an instructor at the Department of Physiology and Biophysics, University of Mississippi Medical Centre – USA (1996 – 1998).

Prof. Kassab is currently on the Executive Committee Board of the Association of Medical Education in the Eastern Mediterranean Region (AMEEMR). Dr. Kassab served also as a WHO consultant in the EMRO region. His areas of research interest in medical education are student engagement, psychometrics, and student assessment. He is a reviewer for top journals in medical education such as *Medical Education* and *Medical Teacher* and is an Editorial board member at *BMC Medical Education* and *Advances in Medical Education & Practice* and a senior editor for *Health Professions Education Journal*. He published around eighty articles in international peer-reviewed Journals in *Medical Education* and *Medical Physiology*.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 2:15 PM - 2:25 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *EVALUATION OF MEDICAL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN ASSIGNMENT PREPARATION USING CHATGPT: CRITERIA OF HIGHLY SUCCESSFUL PROMPTS*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Faten Mahmoud Ali Diab

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Introduction: Learning by writing assignments is a crucial pedagogical element in adult learning as it can improve students' knowledge retention and critical thinking¹. Incorporating AI in medical education aligns with the new international AI paradigm shift wave².

Purpose & Objectives: Objectives: To evaluate the impact of integrating AI tools into medical education by assessing students' performance using ChatGPT in preparing their assignments and clarifying the criteria for highly successful prompts.

Materials & Methods: Materials and Methods: This research was conducted with 83 first-year dental students at GMU. Students were required to submit a scientific graded assignment as part of their physiology coursework. The detailed instructions, learning objectives, and guidelines were shared on Moodle. For the learning resources, the students could use either textbooks, scientific websites, and research articles (Group A: Literature Research Group) or ChatGPT as a helping AI tool (Group B: ChatGPT Group). Students chose their group freely. Also, the students participated in a post-assignment survey comprising 10 MCQs assessing assignment-related knowledge and three short-answer questions to evaluate their experience with ChatGPT during this task.

Findings of Study: Results: 41 chose to join group A, and 42 selected group B and used its free version 3.5. Only 59 students answered the post-assignment survey. The ChatGPT group's mean value of the assignment marks was insignificantly lower, while the mean value of post-assignment exam marks was insignificantly higher than group A. Only 39 students answered the short-answer questions. Regarding: How do you find ChatGPT helpful? The students' answers were gathered into five themes: ChatGPT is fast (51.3%), highly knowledgeable (46.2 %), beneficial for the organization (43.6 %), provides clarification of concepts (20.5 %), and easy (10.2 %). 2. Regarding "What are the difficulties faced? The answers were assembled into four themes: no difficulty (41%), providing biased information with lack of references (48.7%), having limited depth of knowledge (20.5 %), and plagiarism (7.7 %). 3. Regarding the prompts, high achiever students asked ChatGPT for research links and potential websites.

Conclusions: Conclusion: Integrating ChatGPT for assignment preparation does not impact overall performance compared to traditional methods; however, it enhances conceptual understanding and knowledge retention, potentially leading to improved exam outcomes.

Key Words: ChatGPT, assignment

References: 1. Mynlieff M, Manogaran AL, St. Maurice M, Eddinger TJ. Writing assignments with a metacognitive component enhances learning in a large introductory biology course. *CBE Life Sci Educ.* 2014;13(2):311–321. <https://doi.org/10.1187/cbe.13-05-0097>

2. James C, Wheelock K, Woolliscroft J. Academic Medicine. Acad Med. 2021;96(7):954–957. <https://doi.org/10.1097/ACM.0000000000003943>

Biography

Professor Dr. Faten Mahmoud Ali Diab has been a professor of medical physiology since 2008 in the Faculty of Medicine at Ain Shams University. In 2020, she joined the Gulf Medical University in the United Arab Emirates.

She is one of the Scholar Rx advisory board members.

She has been a member of the American Physiological Society (APS) since 2017.

She has been a member of the Physiological Society (UK) since 2017.

She is one of the board judges of the Promotion Scientific Committee of Physiology in Egypt.

She has been a member of the African Association's Physiological Society since 2012.

She has been one of the board member professors in the Egyptian Society of Physiological Sciences since 2012 (ESPS).

She participated on a jury in the promotion scientific committee of physiology at the Esraa University, Jordan.

She is interested in cardiovascular physiology research, especially in the performance of isolated hearts, cardiomyopathy, and vascular physiology. She is greatly interested in attending physiology conferences and physiology workshops.

Also, in 2023, she started her Master's Degree in Medical Health Professional Education at GMU, and she became a member of the International Association for Health Professions Education "AMEE".

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 2:25 PM - 2:35 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *A Cross-Sectional Study on the Impact of Online Teaching During COVID-19 Era on Senior Physiotherapy Students' Clinical Self-Efficacy at Fatima College of Health Sciences, UAE.*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Salwa B. El-Sobkey

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Muhammad Al-Jarrah,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Entry-level physiotherapists function as autonomous healthcare practitioners within a complex healthcare system, requiring professional competence in the clinical domain. Physiotherapy (PT) educational programs typically emphasize onsite teaching and use summative assessments to evaluate students' achievement of program objectives and learning outcomes. However, possessing knowledge and skills does not guarantee efficacy or confidence in clinical practice.

Purpose & Objectives: This study aimed to assess the impact of online teaching approaches, during the COVID-19 era, on the physiotherapy self-efficacy (PSE) of senior FCHS physiotherapy students across three clinical areas: musculoskeletal (MSK), neurological (N), and cardiorespiratory (CR), and to explore the influence of academic factors on PSE scores.

Materials & Methods: Data were collected using a four-section questionnaire to document participants' academic backgrounds and pathways. One section specifically addressed the PSE. The study focused on three cohorts of pre-graduation senior PT students at Fatima College of Health Sciences (FCHS), who experienced a mix of onsite, online, and blended TAs due to COVID-19. Nonparametric statistical analysis was employed to analyze the data.

Findings of Study: Seventeen students participated in the study, representing a 68% participation rate, with a median age of 22 years. The results indicate a statistically significant decrease in self-efficacy from MSK to N, and ultimately to CR clinical areas. The impact of online TAs on PSE varied by courses' specialty; TAs related to CR specialty courses significantly correlated with PSE scores, showing a preference for onsite TA to enhance self-efficacy over blended and online TAs. Furthermore, greater exposure to clinical cases and verbal encouragement from clinical educators were associated with higher self-efficacy. Physiological reactions, such as body pain, were also found to be influenced by the specific clinical area.

Conclusions: The impact of online TAs, implemented during the COVID-19 pandemic, on the self-efficacy of senior PT students is dependent on the specialty of the courses. This impact was most significant in CR specialty courses. Moreover, other factors such as exposure to clinical cases and clinical educator verbal encouragement significantly contributed to students' self-efficacy.

Key Words: Physiotherapy Self-Efficacy, Online Physiotherapy Education, COVID-19 Impact on Health Education, Clinical Competence in Physiotherapy, Student Encouragement in Physiotherapy, Mastery Experiences in Physiotherapy.

References: Black, B., Lucarelli, J., Ingman, M., & Briskey, C. (2016). Changes in physical therapist Students' self-efficacy for physical activity counselling following a motivational interviewing learning module. *Journal of Physical Therapy Education*, 30 (3): 28–33.

Bandura, A. (2005). The evolution of social cognitive theory. In: Smith KD and Hitt MK (eds) *Great Minds in Management*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 9–35.

Biography

Salwa El-Sobkey is an Associate Professor of Physiotherapy at Fatima College of Health Sciences with a rich academic experience spanning 28 years. Her career has taken her across various countries in Egypt and the Gulf Area, contributing significantly to the field of physiotherapy education and practice. She holds a joint Master's degree in Health Professions Education from Maastricht University and Suez Canal University. Salwa is known for her dedication to advancing healthcare through teaching and mentorship. She continues to inspire and lead in the ever-evolving landscape of medical education.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 2:35 PM - 2:45 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Revolutionizing Medical Education: Enhancing Student Engagement and Collaboration with Flipgrid and Poll Everywhere*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Amr Amin

Co-Authors:

- -

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The evolving education landscape demands continual adaptation to engage and empower learners. Technological advancements have ushered in innovative tools like Flipgrid (now part of TEAMS) and Poll Everywhere, explored here for their potential in fostering educational innovation. Flipgrid fosters inclusive discussions via video responses, while Poll Everywhere enables real-time polling, empowering student participation. Conclusion: These tools encourage active learning, critical thinking, and collaboration, reshaping traditional classrooms into dynamic, inclusive environments. Integrating technology caters to diverse learning styles, empowering students to play an active role. Yet, innovation extends beyond tool adoption; educators must align pedagogical strategies and goals. Successful integration requires planning, professional development, and ongoing assessment.

Purpose & Objectives: To assess and improve the classroom engagement of medical students.

Materials & Methods: Flipgrid and Poll Everywhere platforms are employed in this study.

Findings of Study: Technological Integration for Engagement: The abstract emphasizes the significance of leveraging tools like Flipgrid and Poll Everywhere to enhance student engagement and empowerment in education. These platforms facilitate interactive experiences, inclusive discussions, and real-time polling, transforming traditional classrooms into dynamic learning environments.

Holistic Approach to Innovation: The abstract underscores that innovation in education extends beyond the mere implementation of technological tools. Educators must also consider pedagogical strategies, instructional design, and the alignment of educational goals. Successful integration requires thoughtful planning, professional development, and ongoing assessment to ensure meaningful impact on student learning outcomes.

Conclusions: Flipgrid, and Poll Everywhere hold immense potential for enhancing student engagement, critical thinking, and collaboration, preparing them for an evolving world.

Key Words: In-classroom engagement, Flipgrid, Poll Everywhere

References: • https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-319-07293-7_39

- <https://apcz.umk.pl/PBE/article/view/PBE.2021.005>
- <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10125134>

Biography

The focus of Amin's lab is to unravel the cellular and molecular mechanisms of selected natural-based small molecules against gastrointestinal cancers. Through utilizing various cellular & molecular, nanoparticles, bioinformatics, and metabolomics techniques, Amin's lab investigates a variety of biomolecules, aiming to introduce them as potential drug targets. He secured ten patents in the United States, Japan, and Australia. The nature of Amin's research is highly collaborative. Throughout his career, Amin's collaboration's network grew significantly to include over 400 international collaborators from top research institutions worldwide, including Harvard, Stanford, and Oxford, to name a few. He supervised many PhD and MSc theses. His graduate students were recruited to Harvard, ETH Zurich, FRED HUTCHINSON CANCER CENTER, and many other prestigious schools. Prof. Amin published about 150 research articles and invited reviews in top peer-reviewed journals where his students are usually co-authors. Amin is an editorial member and guest editor of many journals. Amin's work in academia has been recognized by multiple national and international awards, including the UAE Presidential "Khalifa Award for Education for University Professors Distinguished in Scientific Research," the "Shoman Award for Arab Researchers," and others.

Date of Presentation: 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 2:45 PM - 2:55 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Online Extended Focused Assessment with Sonography for Trauma (EFAST) Course Enhanced Knowledge and Perceived Confidence Among Medical Trainees during the COVID-19 Pandemic*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Fikri M Abu-Zidan

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Arif Alper Cevik,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted medical education worldwide, prompting the need for innovative e-learning solutions [1, 2].

Purpose & Objectives: This study evaluated the effectiveness of an online extended Focused Assessment with Sonography in Trauma (EFAST) course, delivered via the International Emergency Medicine Education Project's platform, to improve participants' knowledge and perceived confidence in EFAST procedure.

Materials & Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted between May 17, 2020, and December 20, 2023. Pre- and post-course quizzes and surveys were used to assess participants' knowledge and confidence. Participant demographics, quiz scores, and survey responses were collected. Quantitative data were analysed using the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test and Cohen's d to evaluate knowledge improvement and confidence changes. Thematic analysis of qualitative feedback was performed with the assistance of large language model AI tools for emerging themes.

Findings of Study: 1758 participants enrolled in the course. From 111 countries, 1515 started the course, and 1190 (78.6%) reached the final exam stage, with 96.1% achieving a passing score. 66.4% indicated they had never attended a prior ultrasound course. Most (81.1%) were medical students, interns, or residents. 36.5% of participants were from low- or lower-middle-income countries. 1175 (77.6%) participants completed both the pre- and post-course formative knowledge quizzes. The median (IQR) scores were 53.3 (40.0–66.7) pre-course and 86.7 (73.3–93.3) post-course ($p < 0.001$, effect size: -0.958). 771 participants completed both pre- and post-course surveys. Participants' median (IQR) confidence in EFAST increased from 5 (3–7) to 8 (7–10) ($p < 0.001$, effect size: -0.844). Qualitative feedback showed that participants found the course practical, well-structured, and effective. They suggested improving video quality and simplifying content for clarity and engagement.

Conclusions: The online EFAST course enhanced participants' knowledge and perceived confidence, demonstrating the potential of online clinical education during global crises.

Key Words: EFAST, ultrasound education, clinical training, e-learning, remote education, COVID-19

References: 1. TMS Collaborative. The perceived impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on medical student education and training - an international survey. BMC Med Educ. 2021; doi:10.1186/s12909-021-02983-3

2. Walters M, Alonge T, Zeller M. Impact of COVID-19 on Medical Education: Perspectives from Students. Acad Med. 2022; doi:10.1097/ACM.0000000000004525

Biography

Professor Fikri Abu-Zidan: An international expert in Statistics, Research Methodology, Acute Care Surgery, Disaster Medicine, and Point-of-Care Ultrasound. He graduated (MD) from Aleppo University (Syria) in 1981; gained the FRCS, Glasgow, Scotland in 1987; achieved his PhD in Trauma and Disaster Medicine from Linkoping University (Sweden) in 1995; and obtained his Postgraduate Diploma of Applied Statistics from Massey University (New Zealand) in 1999. He is currently serving as a Statistics and Research Methodology Consultant for the World Society of Emergency Surgery. He has made major contributions to trauma and acute care surgery management, education and research in Kuwait, Sweden, New Zealand, Australia, and United Arab Emirates. He has more than 515 publications in books and refereed international journals. He presented more than 830 invited lectures and scientific abstracts, chaired more than 80 scientific sessions, and received more than 40 national and international awards for clinical, research and educational activities.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Using AI-Assisted Storytelling and Simulation in Medical Education: A Pilot Study*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Farah Maree

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Lina Alsheikhmahmoud,
- Dr. Amel Eisa Al Amiri,
- Dr. Saqib Dara,
- Dr. Naren Rajasekarappa,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: In today's digital era of shortened attention spans, medical educators face challenges maintaining learner engagement using traditional lecture-based methods. Storytelling effectively contextualizes and humanizes medical knowledge, yet static case studies offer limited interactivity. By integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) with storytelling, educational content can be dynamically tailored to individual learners, potentially boosting engagement and improving knowledge retention. This study explores the utility of AI-assisted storytelling in medical education compared to conventional teaching approaches, focusing on its effectiveness, learner satisfaction, and long-term impact.

Purpose & Objectives:

1. Evaluate knowledge retention in medical interns taught via AI-assisted storytelling versus conventional methods.
2. Assess learner engagement and satisfaction, and determine whether AI-assisted storytelling enhances the application of knowledge in clinical reasoning.

Materials & Methods: A quasi-experimental pilot study was conducted among a cohort of medical interns (n=36) during their academic day. Participants were randomly divided into two groups: an AI-assisted simulation group (n=18) and a control group experiencing traditional PowerPoint presentations (n=18). Before and after each session, learners completed a brief quiz to measure immediate changes in knowledge. Engagement was assessed using a five-point questionnaire covering motivation, interactivity, and perceived relevance. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize learner responses, and between-group comparisons were evaluated with appropriate tests.

Findings of Study: Preliminary data suggest that learners in the AI-assisted simulation teaching group exhibit stronger engagement scores and slightly improved quiz performance. If corroborated by larger studies, these findings may signify a pivotal role for adaptive technologies in medical curricula. In particular, AI-driven scenarios could promote experiential learning, critical thinking, and higher satisfaction among trainees.

Conclusions: This pilot investigation highlights the potential benefits of integrating AI-facilitated case simulations into medical training. They serve as cost-effective alternatives to manikin simulations. Although limited by a short intervention period and small sample size, the results offer promising insights into how immersive, technology-supported instruction could enrich student experiences. Future work should explore scalability and long-term outcomes to determine its broader applicability.

Key Words: AI-assisted learning, case simulation, medical education

References: 1. Subramanian, A., Timberlake, M., Mittakanti, H., Lara, M., & Brandt, M. L. (2012). Novel educational approach for medical students: improved retention rates using interactive medical software compared with traditional lecture-based format. *Journal of surgical education*, 69(4), 449-452.

2. Chan, K. S., & Zary, N. (2019). Applications and challenges of implementing artificial intelligence in medical education: integrative review. *JMIR medical education*, 5(1), e13930.

Biography

I am an aspiring anesthesiology resident passionate about education, research, and leadership. I have served in several leadership positions, including chief resident for two years and House Staff Committee Council chair, gaining experience in advocacy and program development. My academic interests include patient safety in anesthesia, AI-assisted learning, wellness in medical education, and organizing events and workshops.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *The impact of early clinical exposure on student's professionalism and perception of basic sciences*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Dalia Ali Gaber

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Doaa Mostafa AlEraky,
- Dr. Noha Kamal,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Early clinical exposure (ECE) for undergraduate medical students encompasses a group of supervised activities. It includes early student-patient contact as well as community engagement. Such activities have a positive impact on the development of students' professional knowledge, problem-solving skills, motivation, and active learning. There is a growing body of evidence that students benefit in many ways from ECE. The learning goals of ECE involve shadowing doctors in hospitals, changes in attitudes, ethical principles, and basic skills.

Purpose & Objectives: Assess the impact of early clinical exposure on undergraduate medical students with respect to their perception and professionalism.

Materials & Methods: Implementing our competency-based integrated curriculum, year 2 & year 3 medical students were guided through a tour of the precision medicine research laboratory and Thumbay diagnostic laboratory respectively. The supervising faculty instructed the students about the different departments in the laboratory, the workflow of the biological samples relevant to their future clinical practice. Students were asked to provide their insights in the form of a reflection report, based on Gibb's reflective cycle. Also, focus group discussions were conducted with other students.

Findings of Study: Students reported that their laboratory tour experience connected the dots between the theories they have studied in the theory and their real-world applications, deepening their interest in the research and practical field. They also observed how researchers in the lab actually perform, which enhanced their professional attitude.

Conclusions: From the discussion, it was noticed that students were lacking a clear understanding of how laboratories work in practice—from the initial planning and resource allocation to ensuring the accuracy and precision of patient's results. This activity also revealed a good application of entrepreneurship in establishing their own business. This approach helps us identifying gaps in knowledge and bridge them through practical, work-based experiences and its application. We conclude that implementing early clinical exposure activities during the initial years of medical college is an eye-opener for medical students. It also cultivates medical professionalism before they encounter their official clerkships and internships.

Key Words: Early clinical exposure, Medical professionalism.

- References:** 1. Simmenroth A, Harding A, Vallersnes OM, Dowek A, Carelli F, Kiknadze N, Karppinen H. Early clinical exposure in undergraduate medical education: A questionnaire survey of 30 European countries. *Med Teach.* 2023 Apr;45(4):426-432. doi: 10.1080/0142159X.2022.2137014. Epub 2022 Oct 31. PMID: 36315584.
2. Liu CI, Tang KP, Wang YC, Chiu CH. Impacts of early clinical exposure on undergraduate student professionalism-a qualitative study. *BMC Med Educ.* 2022 Jun 6;22(1):435. doi: 10.1186/s12909-022-03505-5. PMID: 35668444; PMCID: PMC9172165.

Biography

Dr. Dalia is an Associate Professor of Medical Biochemistry & Molecular Biology at the College of Medicine, Gulf Medical University, Ajman, UAE. She is a fellow of medical education (FAIMER) and previously served as the Biochemistry Department Supervisor and Vice Director of the Medical Education Unit at the Faculty of Medicine, Helwan University, Egypt. Dr. Dalia earned her PhD from Ain Shams University, with her thesis published by Lambert Academic Publishing. Her postdoctoral research focuses on cancer genomics, collaborating across various disciplines.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Trend of social media usage by undergraduate medical students; A comparison between medical students and educators*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Ahmed Hafez Ahmed Mohamed Mousa

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Sumera Nisar,
- Dr. Asim Alshanberi,
- Dr. Manal El Said,
- Dr. Fatma El Sayed,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Social media (SM) platforms are becoming increasingly essential for learning, communication and information sharing

Medical students & educators widely use platforms like YouTube, Facebook and WhatsApp for teaching and learning

Social media (SM) facilitates both formal and informal learning beyond the classroom

In the U.S 79.4% of medical students actively use SM for academic purposes, preferring informal methods of learning over conventional class-based teaching

Despite students' enthusiasm, many educators face challenges integrating social media into formal educational practices

Purpose & Objectives: The main aim of the study is to identify the most commonly used social media/networking sites for learning and communication by the medical students and medical educators in a local medical school of Saudi Arabia and to know the gap between the students and the educators in using social media tools for their learning.

Materials & Methods: A cross-sectional study was carried out to assess the trends of usage of SM as an extracurricular way of enhancing learning and teaching experience among medical students and educators in Batterjee Medical College; Saudi Arabia from November 2020 to March 2021.

A pre-validated self-administrated questionnaire was built using Google Drive forms and distributed to medical students and educators via emails and WhatsApp. Convenient sampling was used to collect the data. The questionnaire was initially sent to 150 health educators and students. A total of 128 participants, 101 medical students, and 27 medical educators responded to the survey. The response rate was 85.3%. The missing data were excluded from the study.

The study was approved by Batterjee medical college (BMC), Jeddah, Saudi Arabia research and ethical review committee (RES-2020-0061). Informed verbal and written consent were taken from the students.

The study included medical students from preclinical and clinical years of medicine (M1-M5) and medical educators e.g. professors, associate professors, assistant professors, and lecturers at BMC. Non-medical students and interns were excluded.

The questionnaire consisted of four sections: the first section included questions on student's and educator's demographics (age, gender, year of study, academic post-graduate ranking, and years of experience). The second part was about patterns of SM (usage of SM, frequency, type of SM, and preferred platform). The third part included questions on the use and influence of SM on learning and teaching (influence on education, communication, and collaboration). Finally, participants were also invited to suggest comments that further supported our study. The questionnaire consisted of a Likert-type scale questions (where 1 = strongly disagree, 2 = disagree, 3 = natural, 4 = agree, and 5 = strongly agree), multiple choices, yes/no, and short answer questions.

Analyses was performed with SPSS “statistical package for social sciences” (version 20). Descriptive analyses of the data were represented in tables and graphs in terms of percentages and used to estimate the frequency and prevalence of using SM for learning purposes.

Findings of Study: The total number of respondents was 101 medical students and 27 educators in the survey. Females represented 64.4% (n = 65) of the total participants. The majority of participants belonged to the clinical sciences (60.4%; 61/101).

The most common websites used by students for their learning were YouTube (92.1%, n = 93) and Blackboard (63.3%, n = 64).

Most students (90.6%) used SM for learning for at least 1 h per day or more.

The preferred device to use when students attend sessions or educators teaching students was the laptop by 57.4% (n = 58) and in 62.9% (n = 17) respectively followed by the tablet.

Conclusions: Social media has immense potential to enhance its role in educational settings. Both the students and educators use it for communication, education, sharing and expressing knowledge, and recreation. Their contemporary and efficient use cannot be overlooked by educators. To use them to their fullest; the material posted needs evaluation to be accurate, concise, and engaging. Moreover, choosing the right platform, the amount and quality of the information shared to ensure optimal benefit, providing ethical guides, and professional standards for SM use at institutional levels are the few challenges that need to address.

Key Words: Social media, medical education, online learning resources

References: 1. Whyte W, Hennessy C. Social Media use within medical education: a systematic review to develop a pilot questionnaire on how social media can be best used at BSMS. MedEdPublish. 2017;6

2. Latif MZ, Hussain I, Saeed R, Qureshi MA, Maqsood U. Use of smart phones and social media in medical education: trends, advantages, challenges and barriers. Acta Inf. Med. 2019;27(2)

Biography

Dr. Ahmed Hafez Mousa, MD (Hons) is currently a neurosurgery resident in the Saudi Board Neurosurgery Residency Program at Dubai Health - Mohammed Bin Rashid University of Medicine and Health Sciences. Dr. Mousa has completed his bachelors of medicine and surgery with honors from Batterjee Medical College in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. Dr. Mousa is an active researcher with over 55 peer-reviewed publications in prestigious journals. Moreover, Dr. Mousa is has constantly held

various leadership positions throughout his career, most recent one being the trainee representative for neurosurgery at the Graduate Medical Education unit at Dubai Health. Dr. Mousa enjoys public speaking, community volunteering and teaching. He is a TEDx speaker in which he gave a talk titled (Better not more: The Dilemma of Perfection) on how quantitative requirements negatively affect students in comparison to how focus on quality should be made first. Outside of work, Dr. Mousa enjoys spending time with his parents, playing basketball and getting involved with philanthropic community initiatives.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *The Role of Quality Improvement Projects in Advancing Dental Internship Training in the UAE*

Presenter's Name: Dr. May Al Janahi

Co-Authors:

- -

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The healthcare system in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) is undergoing significant development, propelled by a robust dedication to provide exemplary medical and dental services. This expansion requires a skilled workforce capable of providing advanced patient care in alignment with international standards. Dental education, particularly at the internship stage, is crucial in cultivating proficient practitioners who can meet the UAE's diverse patient needs. To achieve this, it is essential for interns to acquire not only clinical skills but also quality management capabilities, particularly through Quality Improvement (QI) projects. Integrating QI projects in dental internships is therefore a powerful strategy for advancing clinical excellence, enhancing patient outcomes, and fulfilling the UAE's commitment to high standards in healthcare.

Engaging dental interns in QI projects during their training builds a holistic approach to patient care that adheres to international standards. QI projects empower interns to systematically evaluate clinical practices, identify areas for improvement, and implement evidence-based interventions. This hands-on process fosters critical thinking, adaptability, and accountability, giving interns direct experience in upholding clinical standards and enhancing care protocols. Such initiatives are particularly relevant in the UAE, where healthcare excellence is a national priority, and reflect both local and global expectations for clinical quality.

Purpose & Objectives: The purpose of incorporating Quality Improvement (QI) projects into dental internship training in the UAE is to equip future practitioners with essential skills that align with national healthcare goals and international standards. Through QI projects, dental interns develop clinical competence and adaptability, enhancing their ability to deliver high-quality patient care. By fostering critical thinking and analytical skills, interns become adept at identifying and resolving clinical challenges, which strengthens their professional responsibility and accountability in impacting patient outcomes. This patient-centered approach promotes safety, satisfaction, and effective communication, central components in advancing healthcare excellence.

The program also encourages a culture of continuous improvement, instilling habits of lifelong learning that are essential in an evolving healthcare landscape. Working in interdisciplinary teams allows interns to enhance their collaboration and teamwork skills, a crucial aspect of modern healthcare delivery. Additionally, QI projects bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, offering interns hands-on experience in real-world clinical improvement. By providing foundational knowledge in quality management, these projects prepare interns to take on roles in advanced healthcare environments. Ultimately, QI initiatives support the UAE's vision by

cultivating a generation of skilled, quality-focused dental practitioners who are prepared to address the country's expanding healthcare needs.

Materials & Methods: A number of studies highlight the benefits that dental interns perceive from engaging in Quality Improvement (QI) projects during their training. Interns report that QI initiatives enhance their problem-solving skills and foster critical thinking, as these projects require systematic assessment and improvement of clinical processes.

Findings of Study: For the past few years, interns at Dubai Health have participated in QI projects where they were organized into groups to examine areas such as documentation practices and time-out procedures. They completed three improvement cycles, reporting these initiatives as beneficial and aligning their experiences with findings from similar studies.

Conclusions: Quality Improvement (QI) projects are essential in dental internships, as they offer hands-on experience in systematically analyzing and enhancing clinical practices. Through structured QI initiatives, interns develop critical skills in identifying gaps, implementing solutions, and evaluating outcomes, fostering both adaptability and accountability.

Embedding QI project skills within internship training equips dental interns with essential evaluative and improvement-oriented competencies, instilling a mindset of continuous improvement and patient-centered care. Actively participating in QI initiatives enables interns to bridge the gap between academic learning and clinical application, thereby strengthening their professional responsibilities and clinical skills.

Key Words: Quality improvement project, audit, dental internship

References: Salim, R., Al-Azazi, M., & Zayed, A. (2021). Preparing UAE dental graduates for the healthcare workforce: Challenges and solutions. *International Journal of Health Education*, 15(3), 134-140.

Sultan, L., & Al-Bader, H. (2023). Quality improvement in dental internships: Impacts on clinical excellence and patient care in the UAE. *UAE Journal of Dental Practice*, 12(1), 56-65

Biography

Dr. May Al Janahi is a Specialist Prosthodontist with a Doctor of Clinical Dentistry (DClinDent) in Prosthodontics from the University of Edinburgh and is a member of the Royal College of Surgeons, UK. She serves as Program Director for the Dental Internship at Mohammed Bin Rashid University of Medicine and Health Sciences (MBRU) and is core faculty for the Master of Science in Prosthodontics program. Additionally, Dr. May is a member of the Graduate Medical Education Committee at Dubai Health, where she oversees training and accreditation for healthcare trainees.

Dr. May's expertise includes treating complex cases like full mouth rehabilitation, with prosthetic solutions that address diverse patient needs, including removable and fixed prostheses and implant-supported options. Passionate about advancing her field, she combines clinical expertise with a commitment to mentorship, empowering young dental professionals to uphold high standards in patient-centered prosthodontic care. Dr. May is dedicated to advancing healthcare for young dentists, integrating digital dentistry to enhance clinical outcomes and prepare her mentees to lead in a fast-evolving field. She fosters a collaborative environment with students and specialists to ensure each patient receives comprehensive, personalized care.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *The influence of personality traits on academic performance of dental undergraduates in Ajman University, Ajman, UAE.*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Alexander Maniangat Luke

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Dana Shaher Abdelwahab,
- Dr. Lama Mohammed Alamasy,
- Dr. Aya Mohammed Haidary,
- Dr. Simy Mathew,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Background: Personality impact people's lives in significant ways, which helps to explain why two people in comparable situations frequently have different results. Personality has been shown to play a vital and prominent role in academic achievement and motivation. Based on previous studies, some personality traits have been shown to be linked strongly with academic performance, among which the strongest correlations being conscientiousness (positively) and neuroticism (negatively).

Purpose & Objectives: The aim of this study is to assess the relationship between personality and academic performance among dental students using The Big Five Personality Trait scale.

Materials & Methods: Methods: A cross-sectional survey using the Big Five Personality Trait scale was distributed among 360 dental students. A response rate of 77% was achieved.

Findings of Study: Results: No correlation between extroversion and AGPA was present, however, a negative correlation between AGPA and neuroticism was found as well as a positive correlation between openness, conscientiousness, and agreeableness.

Conclusions: Conclusion: Personality traits can be associated with an individual's potential in the dentistry profession. The findings revealed that individual variations in personality traits both directly and indirectly contribute to students' academic achievement.

Key Words: dental student; big five personality; AGPA

References: [1] Richardson, M., Abraham, C., & Bond, R. (2012). Psychological correlates of university students' academic performance: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 138(2), 353–387. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0026838>

[2] Sander, P., & De La Fuente, J. (2020). Undergraduate Student Gender, Personality and Academic Confidence. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(15), 5567. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17155567>

Biography

Dr Alexander Maniangat Luke has completed his Bachelor's degree from Bangalore University followed by a Masters degree in Oral Medicine and Radiology from Rajiv Gandhi University. Furthermore he went on to pursue fellowships in Laser Dentistry from Italy and USA. He was awarded the Fellowship of the Royal College of Physicians and Surgeons of Glasgow(FDS RCPS) in 2021. He has an experience of over 20 years in academics as well as clinical practice. In addition, he has keen interest in research and has many publications contributing to his field of expertise. He is a member of the International Association of DentoMaxilloFacial Radiology, Indian Academy of Oral Medicine and Radiology and the Asian Academy of Oral and Maxillo-Facial Radiology. He joined Ajman University, College of Dentistry, Ajman in the January, 2010. He currently hold the rank of Assistant Professor and also serves as the Radiation Protection Officer at Ajman University, College of Dentistry.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Are Medical Students Ready for the Forthcoming Integration of AI into Medical Practice? A Cross-sectional Study*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Saif Mohamad Ismail Sultan Alolama Alkhaaldi

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Carl H Kassab,
- Dr. Leen Oyouun Alsoud,
- Dr. Cynthia Al Hageh,
- Dr. Halah Ibrahim,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Artificial intelligence (AI) has the potential to revolutionize the way medicine is learned, taught, and practiced, and medical education must prepare learners for these inevitable changes. Academic medicine has, however, been slow to embrace recent AI advances. Since its launch in November 2022, ChatGPT has emerged as a fast and user-friendly large language model that can assist health care professionals, medical educators, students, trainees, and patients. While many studies focus on the technology's capabilities, potential, and risks, there is a gap in studying the perspective of end users.

Purpose & Objectives: The aim of this study was to gauge the experiences and perspectives of graduating medical students on ChatGPT and AI in their training and future careers.

Materials & Methods: A cross-sectional web-based survey of recently graduated medical students was conducted in an international academic medical center between May 5, 2023, and June 13, 2023. Descriptive statistics were used to tabulate variable frequencies.

Findings of Study: Of 325 applicants to the residency programs, 265 completed the survey (an 81.5% response rate). The vast majority of respondents denied using ChatGPT in medical school, with 20.4% (n=54) using it to help complete written assessments and only 9.4% using the technology in their clinical work (n=25). More students planned to use it during residency, primarily for exploring new medical topics and research (n=168, 63.4%) and exam preparation (n=151, 57%). Male students were significantly more likely to believe that AI will improve diagnostic accuracy (n=47, 51.7% vs n=69, 39.7%; P=.001), reduce medical error (n=53, 58.2% vs n=71, 40.8%; P=.002), and improve patient care (n=60, 65.9% vs n=95, 54.6%; P=.007). Previous experience with AI was significantly associated with positive AI perception in terms of improving patient care, decreasing medical errors and misdiagnoses, and increasing the accuracy of diagnoses (P=.001, P<.001, P=.008, respectively).

Conclusions: The surveyed medical students had minimal formal and informal experience with AI tools and limited perceptions of the potential uses of AI in health care but had overall positive views of ChatGPT and AI and were optimistic about the future of AI in medical education and health care. Structured curricula and formal policies and guidelines are needed to adequately prepare medical learners for the forthcoming integration of AI in medicine.

Key Words: Medical education; ChatGPT; artificial intelligence; large language models; AI; medical students.

References: N/A

Biography

I am a third year medical student at Khalifa University and I hold a Bachelor's degree in biomedical engineering. I have always been interested in research throughout my studies from topics on biomedical engineering to medicine and medical education. Recently, we published a paper on the perception of ChatGPT by medical students and trainees with the aim of taking the new technologies and AI into consideration when developing medical curricula to prepare future doctors for the integration of AI into medical practice. Moreover, we are currently conducting another research on the awareness of medical students and trainees on climate change and its bidirectional relationship with healthcare. A solid framework is needed to prepare future physicians achieve sustainable practices and tackle climate-induced health issues.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Experiences and Perceptions of Medical Students on Climate Change: A Cross-Sectional Survey Study*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Saif Mohamad Ismail Sultan Alolama Alkhaaldi

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Leen Oyouun Alsoud,
- Dr. Cynthia Al Hageh,
- Dr. Halah Ibrahim,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Climate change is one of the biggest environmental challenges of the 21st century, imposing direct threats to human health and contributing to 23% of deaths globally. Physicians are at the forefront of recognizing, preventing, and treating climate-induced health issues and should serve as role models in supporting sustainable practices. The effects of climate change are pronounced in the arid and semi-arid regions of the Middle East and Northern Africa (MENA) due to heat extremes, water scarcity, and air pollution. Yet, there is limited published data from the region on physicians' climate change-related training and knowledge.

Purpose & Objectives: This study aims to understand medical trainee perceptions, training, and knowledge of climate change and its impact on health.

Materials & Methods: A cross-sectional web-based survey of medical students in the United Arab Emirates was conducted between May 6,- July 9, 2024. Mean composite Likert scales were calculated, and R software was used to determine the associations.

Findings of Study: Of the 232 responses received, respondents were predominantly between 25 and 30 years old (n=132; 56.9%) and attended medical schools in the MENA region (n=160; 69%). Most respondents did not receive climate change education in their curriculum (n=146; 62.93%) and only 38.4% (n=89) felt knowledgeable about addressing climate change in their patient care. Less than half of student respondents were willing to take steps to personally mitigate climate change hazards, such as using public transportation (n=93; 40.10%) or receiving a lower salary as a resident to support hospital initiatives (n=63; 27.16%). There was no significant association between climate change education and overall attitude or knowledge score.

Conclusions: Medical students in the region had limited training in climate change and reported and most were unlikely to adopt behaviors to mitigate climate change, thus underscoring the need for inculcating climate change and adaptation strategies into the medical curriculum. A solid framework is needed to prepare future physicians to address the challenges posed by climate change and educate them on balancing optimal individual care while promoting public health.

Key Words: Medical education; climate change; carbon footprint; medical practice; medical students.

References: N/A

Biography

I am a third year medical student at Khalifa University and I hold a Bachelor's degree in biomedical engineering. I have always been interested in research throughout my studies from topics on biomedical engineering to medicine and medical education. Recently, we published a paper on the perception of ChatGPT by medical students and trainees with the aim of taking the new technologies and AI into consideration when developing medical curricula to prepare future doctors for the integration of AI into medical practice. Moreover, we are currently conducting another research on the awareness of medical students and trainees on climate change and its bidirectional relationship with healthcare. A solid framework is needed to prepare future physicians achieve sustainable practices and tackle climate-induced health issues.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Assessing the Impact of Microsoft Planner on Task Management for GME Program Coordinators: Enhancing Efficiency and Productivity- A Pilot*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Roaa Al Sardy

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Nora Noureldin,
- Dr. Ayesha Saeed Khamis ALAraj ALMheiri ,
- Dr. Rasha Buhmaid ,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Graduate Medical Education (GME) program coordinators bear a multitude of responsibilities that are essential for the smooth operation of GME programs. Efficient task management is critical, yet challenging, due to the complexity and volume of tasks. Microsoft Planner, a task management and collaboration tool, offers potential solutions for enhancing organization and productivity.

Purpose & Objectives: This pilot aimed to evaluate the impact of Microsoft Planner on task management capabilities among GME program coordinators, focusing on improvements in task organization, prioritization, collaboration, and overall productivity.

Materials & Methods: A cohort of 14 GME program coordinators participated in the pilot. The pilot involved a pre- and post-intervention design, where coordinators used Microsoft Planner over a three-month period. Data were collected through surveys measuring task management efficiency and perceived productivity.

Findings of Study: Initial results showed that Microsoft Planner could potentially enhance task organization and prioritization, enabling coordinators to manage their workload more effectively. At the conclusion of the pilot, the program coordinators will be surveyed on their satisfaction and challenges related to the use of this technology.

Conclusions: The implementation of Microsoft Planner could positively impact task management for GME program coordinators by improving efficiency and productivity. Adoption of such digital tools should be considered by medical education programs to enhance operational success and coordinator satisfaction. Future research could explore long-term impacts and integration with other technological solutions.

Key Words: GME Program Coordinator, Task Management

References: ACGME, Program coordinator Handbook.

<https://www.acgme.org/globalassets/pdfs/coordinators/program-coordinator-handbook.pdf>

ACGME, Additional Resources for program coordinators.

<https://www.acgme.org/additional-resources/>

Biography

Roaa is a dedicated healthcare professional with a strong background in pharmacy and a passion for medication safety and medical education. With a degree in Pharmacy, she has gained nine years of experience in the field, specializing in Medication Safety and Patient Education.

Her commitment to excellence in medication management is complemented by her recent focus on Graduate Medical Education (GME), which she began four years ago.

Currently, Roaa works in the GME office at Mohammed Bin Rashid University of Medicine and Health Sciences, where she is responsible for Program Accreditations. In this capacity, she plays a role in ensuring that medical education programs meet the highest standards, contributing to the development of future healthcare professionals.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Impact of Integrated Teaching Approach on the Knowledge Acquisition and Cognitive Load of Dental Students*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Pooja Narain Adtani

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Ramya Rathan,
- Dr. Mohammed Shoaib,
- Dr. Walid Elsayed,
- Dr. Hesham Marei,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: A competent dental graduate performs several surgical procedures that requires a solid foundation of anatomy, making head and neck anatomy course an indispensable component of the dental education curriculum. However, several studies have reported that learning head and neck anatomy by dental students is perceived as a cognitively challenging subject, where students face the issue of content difficulty and cognitive overload.

Purpose & Objectives: The present study aimed to investigate the effect of integrating oral radiology and head and neck anatomy teaching on the cognitive load and knowledge acquisition of first-year dental students.

Materials & Methods: The study design was an experimental type (cross-over) that included first-year undergraduate dental students (N=82). Students were divided into two groups (G), G1 & G2. G1 was exposed to a teaching session of anatomy, while G2 was exposed to an integrated session of anatomy and oral radiology and vice versa.

A comparison of the Intrinsic Cognitive Load (ICL) and the Extrinsic Cognitive Load (ECL) at the end of each session was evaluated using a standardized and validated questionnaire. For evaluation of knowledge acquisition, both groups answered 20 knowledge and application-based anatomy multiple choice questions (MCQs) for 30 minutes. The content of the MCQs was approved and validated by subject experts.

Data analysis was performed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. The parametric Independent student t-test and non-parametric Man Whitney U test were performed to analyze the research study objectives.

Findings of Study: The results indicated a statistically significant difference between the cognitive load of students in the integrated sessions with complex topics, while there was no significant statistical difference between the mean performance scores of G1 and G2.

Conclusions: This study offers insight into the importance of incorporating the principles of CLT in an integrated teaching approach for effective head and neck anatomy learning.

Integrating head and neck anatomy with oral radiology suggested low cognitive load but no effect on the knowledge acquisition of novice dental students. Our findings emphasize the need to teach complex head and neck anatomy topics in an integrated format.

Key Words: Cognitive Load, Dental Education, Head and neck anatomy, radiology

References: Chew, C., O'Dwyer, P. J., Young, D. & Gracie, J. A. (2020). Radiology teaching improves Anatomy scores for medical students. *British Journal of Radiology*, 93(1114).

Leppink, J., Paas, F., Van der Vleuten, C. P. M., Van Gog, T. & Van Merriënboer, J. J. G. (2013). Development of an instrument for measuring different types of cognitive load. *Behavior Research Methods*, 45(4), 1058–1072.

Biography

Dr. Pooja Adtani is currently the Assistant Professor of Oral Histopathology at the College of Dentistry, Gulf Medical University, Ajman since 2017. She graduated from Bharati Vidhyapeeth Deemed University, Pune and received her Master's and Doctoral degree from Sri Ramachandra Institute of Higher Education and Research (SRIHER), Chennai, India in collaboration with the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR), New Delhi, India.

Her research interest includes developing a 'targeted antifibrotic therapy for Oral Fibrosis'. She has worked extensively on the molecular pathways involved in oral fibrosis particularly the TGFbeta/Smad pathway with active phytoconstituents and plant extracts.

Dr. Pooja has several publications to her credit in various international and national indexed journals. She also has several appreciation certificates awarded following participation and contributions in national and international dental congresses, conferences and workshops.

She is zealous about learning innovative teaching and learning strategies to enhance student learning and performance. This interest led her to pursue the 'Master's in Health Profession Education' (JMHPE) program offered by GMU in collaboration with the Foundation for Advancement of International Medical Education and Research (FAIMER). She was awarded the master's degree in Health Professions Education in 2021.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *THE PREVALENCE AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS AMONG STUDENTS IN A MEDICAL UNIVERSITY IN DUBAI*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Seba Anas Mohammed Saleh

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Goumana Hany,
- Dr. Hind Marwan,
- Dr. Rasha Eldeeb,
- Dr. Dalia Diary Abdulrahman,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Medical students constantly confront obstacles to their educational prospects, both external and internal, which affect their mental health. In addition to the stress of the medical curriculum students experience higher rates and prevalence of psychological distress as a result of the pressure to maintain a high standard of performance.

Purpose & Objectives: This study aims to assess the prevalence of psychological distress among medical students and investigate its associated factors.

Materials & Methods: 154 medical and pharmacy students were included in a quantitative observational cross-sectional design survey. The survey questionnaire has 3 sections: The sociodemographic section, Kessler's Screening tool, and the personal and academic factors.

Findings of Study: Results:

The majority (62.2%) were likely to have severe psychological distress. 67.8% reported studying less than 4 hours/day, 59.6% had less than 6 hours of sleep/night, 20.1% were engaged in physical activity more than once per week and 80.5% were not living in the university hostel. Psychological distress was higher among students living in the university hostel and those who didn't exercise more than once/week.

Discussion:

Medical school is a stressful environment that exerts a negative effect on the academic performance, physical health, and psychological well-being of the students. This study follows other studies that showed that 41.9% of medical students were found to have psychological stress.

Conclusions: The high prevalence of psychological distress among medical students is associated with multiple factors such as the number of hours spent in study, sleep, and exercise; students' ability to cope with the stress of the medical curriculum, living away from family, and communicating with the medical staff.

Key Words: Psychological distress , Medical students , Academic performance

References: 1- Aktekin, M.; Karaman, T.; Senol, Y.Y.; Erdem, S.; Erengin, H.; Akaydin, M. Anxiety, depression and stressful life events among medical students: A prospective study in Antalya, Turkey. *Med. Educ.* 2001, 35, 12–17.

2- Drapeau A, Marchand A, Beaulieu Prévost D. Epidemiology of psychological distress. In: L'Abate L, editor. *Mental Illnesses – Understanding, Prediction and Control*. Ch. 5. Rijeka, Croatia: InTech; 2011. p. 105–34.

Biography

Greetings , I would like to introduce to you myself Seba and my colleges from Dubai Medical College For girls , We are a group of enthusiastic medical students and Physicians having enormous passion in Research , and this time we wanted to assess "THE PREVALENCE AND ASSOCIATED FACTORS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS AMONG STUDENTS IN A MEDICAL UNIVERSITY IN DUBAI". We Would love to present a poster about our research at your valuable conference . Regards !

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Role of Interview in selection of candidates for Medical Internship Program*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Saria Gouher

Co-Authors:

- -

Abstract

Background & Introduction: INTRODUCTION:

The interview for entry into graduate medical education is an important step in the selection process apart from other knowledge based criteria of exam grades ,it allows assessment of noncognitive factors and assess the mutual fit of the applicant and the program. Ideally, the interview contributes to the final rank list by systematically assessing personal qualities, skills, and competencies¹. The screening, interview, and ranking processes are critical, as applicant selection has enduring consequences for the programs. Ideally, an applicant should be a good “fit” for the program, with a high likelihood of success and a low likelihood of problems. Poor performance in training may require remediation, which can create significant workflow issues, reduce morale, and have a negative impact on future recruitment.¹

The internship program in the UAE is a one-year training initiative designed for medical graduates, serving as a prerequisite for entry into residency programs. The selection of interns for this program significantly impacts both the hospital faculty and the interns themselves. Hospitals aim to have their teams embody their vision to provide exemplary service to patients. For faculty members, this means selecting team players who can collaborate effectively. For interns, the goal is to gain hands-on experience in healthcare as novice physicians, ultimately transitioning into independent practitioners.

The selection process to meet these objectives involves multiple stages. Initially, applicants undergo a preliminary screening conducted by Dubai Health Authority authority, the sponsoring institution, which involves the successful submission of required documentation. During this process, each applicant is also asked to rank their preferred hospitals, and this information is subsequently forwarded to the respective hospitals.

Upon receiving the list of applicants, participating hospitals send out interview invitations. A committee of faculty members is then assembled to carry out the interviews. The primary challenge at this stage is to select the interns who are the best fit for the program. To ensure consistency, a standardized set of questions is posed to each applicant, and their responses are scored and compiled into a ranking.

Purpose & Objectives: To assess the validity of the interview questions, the correlation between the interview scores and the interns' overall performance throughout the year is analyzed, helping to predict the effectiveness of the selection process in achieving the desired program outcomes.

Materials & Methods: METHODS:

The interview questions were crafted to explore candidates' personalities, local healthcare experience, and research background and they were expected to provide detailed description of any memorable patient experience, allowing us to assess their understanding of patient healthcare journey, as well as qualities like empathy, teamwork, intellectual curiosity, and motivation. Additionally, candidates were given the opportunity to express any questions they had about the program at the end of the interview.

We gathered the scores from the intern selection interviews and the average evaluation scores from their clinical rotations during the first eight months of training. The interview scores were based on six questions, with a maximum score of 60, while the mean evaluations were based on a total score of 100, reflecting the average scores obtained over the eight months of the internship year.

Findings of Study: RESULTS: The Data for the interview scores and mean evaluation scores were collected and analyzed with calculation of correlation coefficient.

Results of the pearson correlation indicated that there is a significant large positive relationship between Interview scores (X) and Mean Evaluation scores (Y), ($r(14) = .739$, $p = .001$).

Conclusions: DISCUSSION:

The selection of interns is crucial for ensuring that programs can deliver efficient, safe, timely, and high-value care to patients. The qualities sought during the selection process are aimed at identifying candidates who are the best fit for these objectives. Traits such as being personable, trustworthy, diligent, and self-directed learners² are commonly found in high-performing trainees.

This paper highlights the importance of the interview in the selection process, emphasizing the specific attributes the program seeks in candidates and how well the interview questions correlate with the interns' performance during their rotations, meeting the program's expectations. Although the training lasts only one year and does not significantly disrupt the workflow, choosing candidates who can function as effective team players within the hospital remains essential. The current correlation scores reinforce our confidence that the interview questions, which focus on the interns' personalities, local experience, intellectual curiosity, and research interests, are effective in identifying the best candidates for our programs.

Key Words: Interview, Best fit , Internship

References:

1. Use of the Interview in Resident Candidate Selection: A Review of the Literature
Alyssa Stephenson-Famy, MD, Brenda S. Houmard, MD, PhD, Sidharth Oberoi, BS, Anton Manyak, BS, Seine Chiang, MD, and Sara Kim, PhD;
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4675409/>
2. What makes a "great resident": the resident perspective; Venu M. Nemani, Caroline Park, and Danyal H. Nawabi.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/?term=Nemani%20VM%5BAuthor%5D>

Biography

MEDICAL EDUCATION

- 8/2005 – 8/2008 Internal Medicine Residency University at Buffalo- Catholic Health System Internal Medicine Residency Program at Sisters of Charity Hospital, Buffalo, New York, USA.
- 10/1995 - 6/2001. M.B; B.S. Degree Deccan College of Medical Sciences, N.T.R. University of Health Sciences, A.P. India

CERTIFICATIONS:

- ABIM (American Board of Internal Medicine): Recer_fied - Valid _ll 12/2027
- Certificate in AI in Healthcare - Harvard T H Chan School of Public Health Feb 2024
- Certified Patient Experience Professional ,Pa_ent Experience Ins_tute ;November 2023
- Member, American College of Physicians
- Member, Emirates Medical Associa_on
- Alumni, Harvard Macy Ins_tute, USA

MEDICAL LICENSURE:

- Dubai Health Authority, UAE 2010-Present
- Louisiana State Board of Medical Examiners, USA 2008-2010
- Andhra Pradesh Medical Council, India 2001- Present

CLINICAL EXPERIENCE

- Consultant Internal Medicine, American Hospital 2010- _ll present
- Director , Division of Hospital Medicine, American Hospital 9/2012- 9/2022
- Attending Physician, Ochsner St.Anne General Hospital,USA 2008- 2010

ACADEMIC EXPERIENCE :

- Associate DIO , Graduate Medical Education, AHD
- Program Director , Medical Internship Program (2022-Present)and Coordinator Medical School Clerkship Programs (2021-present)
- Adjunct Clinical Assistant Professor of Internal Medicine , University of Sharjah School of Medical Sciences and GMU ; 10/2019 _ll Present

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *From chalkboards to chatrooms: the new normal in medical education*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Safia Rehman

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The COVID-19 pandemic triggered a rapid shift from traditional in-person medical education to remote learning platforms, fundamentally altering the educational landscape for students and educators alike.

Purpose & Objectives: To examine the challenges faced by students and educators during the transition to online medical education.

To highlight the advantages and innovations that emerged from this shift.

To discuss the implications for the future of medical education.

Materials & Methods: Analysis of available literature on online learning during the pandemic.

Review of surveys and studies on student and educator experiences.

Observation of changes in teaching methods and technological adoption.

Findings of Study: Challenges: Limited access to technology, difficulties in online engagement, and concerns about remote assessment integrity.

Advantages: Enhanced global connectivity, innovative teaching methods, and access to a broader range of resources.

Implications: Need for equitable technology access, increased flexibility in learning modalities, and ongoing innovation in educational practices.

Conclusions: The pandemic has permanently altered medical education by highlighting the need for equitable access to technology and the value of flexible learning models. Future efforts should focus on maintaining innovations, addressing mental health concerns, and ensuring a supportive educational environment.

Key Words: Medical Education, Remote Learning, COVID-19, Educational Innovation, Technology Equity

References: Sandars, J., et al. (2020). Twelve tips for rapidly migrating to online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. *MedEdPublish*, 9(1), 82.

Dost, S., et al. (2020). Perceptions of medical students towards online teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic: a national cross-sectional survey of 2721 UK medical students. *BMJ Open*, 10(11), e042378.

Biography

Dr. Safia Rehman is a Consultant Radiologist and Nuclear Medicine Physician at Sheikh Shakhbout Medical City (SSMC) in Abu Dhabi. With a Postgraduate Certificate in Medical Education from the University of Dundee, she blends her passion for teaching with her clinical work. She trained at Oxford University Hospitals and was a consultant at University Hospitals Birmingham previously. Her areas of expertise include hybrid imaging, nuclear cardiology, neurological nuclear medicine, radionuclide therapies, and general/emergency radiology. She was a Fellow of the Royal College of Radiologists, United Kingdom and completed her MSc in Nuclear Medicine from King's College London, UK.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *The structure of resilience in the preclinical phase medical students in the United Arab Emirates.*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Mariam Shadan

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Emma Rawling Smith,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The recent introduction of the Emirates-meds competency framework in the United Arab Emirates (UAE) not only highlights the country's commitment to enhancing the quality and standardization of medical education but also underscores a crucial focus on nurturing resilience among undergraduates. This emphasis reflects a recognition of the challenges posed by professional stress and a dedication to fostering essential resilience-building skills.

Purpose & Objectives: The attempt to prescribe a single idea to a complex trait like resilience is at best naïve and at worst damaging, both to individuals and to the education system. Drawing on data from preclinical phase medical students in the UAE, this mixed method study aims to explore three things: first to evaluate the overall impact of demographic variables such as gender, nationality, and year of the program on resilience; second to explore the factors that enhanced this trait; and finally, to assess if there is variation in resilience promoting attributes between students.

Materials & Methods: I used two psychometric tools, namely the Resilience Scale-14 (RS-14) (Wagnild and Young, 2003) and Academic resilience scale-30 (ARS-30) (Cassidy, 2015), and an interpretivist approach to analyse and understand the subjective meanings of resilience through the stressful experiences of the students within their contexts.

Findings of Study: The study's findings reveal that there is no statistically significant relationship between resilience and the demographic characteristics of medical students. Moreover, the research highlights a substantial overlap and interdependence among the intrinsic and extrinsic factors that contribute to students' resilience. Notably, resilience demonstrates predictive relationships with academic resilience, suggesting that individuals with higher resilience levels are better equipped to thrive in academically challenging situations. This research addresses the scarcity of studies on resilience in the UAE region and offers a comprehensive understanding of resilience within the context of students' experiences.

Conclusions: The study's findings underscore the necessity of implementing a well-structured curriculum that emphasizes psychological resilience. Additionally, medical institutions should prioritize the creation of supportive learning environments that promote mental and emotional well-being. The RS-14 scale can serve as a valuable tool for assessing the development of this crucial attribute among medical students. As the medical profession becomes increasingly demanding, possessing resilience is essential for not only surviving but also thriving in this field.

Key Words: Resilience; Medical education; competency

References: Cassidy, S. J. (2015). Resilience Building in Students: The Role of Academic Self- efficacy. *Front. Psychol.*, (6). <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2015.01781>

Wagnild, G. M., Young, H.M. (1993). Development and psychometric evaluation of the resilience scale. *Journal of Nursing Measurement*, 1(2), 165-178.

Biography

Dr. Mariam Shadan is an Assistant Professor of Biomedical Sciences (Pathology) at Dubai Medical College for Girls. In her role, she engages in curriculum development, medical education research, and leadership initiatives to advance medical education.

Dr. Shadan holds an MD in Pathology from Aligarh Muslim University and an MSc in Medical Education from the University of Oxford. She aims to bridge traditional academia with modern educational approaches. Her research focuses on creating culturally diverse, student-centered curricula and developing resilience frameworks for medical schools.

Recognized with the Best Medical Education Poster Award from the University of Oxford in 2023, Dr. Shadan is a published author dedicated to continually advancing in the dynamic field of medicine, pathology and medical education.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Unlocking Trainee Wisdom: Using the Troika tool to improve peer-to-peer coaching amongst trainee doctors.*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Seher Ahmad

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The Troika tool is a novel method of coaching that encourages quick round-robin 'consultations', where individuals ask for help and get advice immediately from two other trainees. This method of peer-to-peer coaching allows trainee doctors to discover effective solutions to challenges using the collective wisdom of their peers. This simple and effective way to extend mutual support encourages trust in groups and uses teamwork to create an environment for unimagined solutions to emerge.

Purpose & Objectives: To evaluate whether internal Medicine Residents benefit from peer-to-peer coaching.

To understand if coaching residents requires a hierarchical/top-down approach or whether fellow residents are able to support the learning needs of each other.

Materials & Methods: The Troika coaching tool splits trainees into groups of three.

Each trainee took it in turns to be 'coached' for 10 minutes.

For the first 2 minutes, the coachee shared their challenging situation.

The next 2 minutes involved coaches asking clarifying questions.

In the following 4 minutes, the coachee turned around to face away from the circle whilst the coaches discussed the challenging problem between themselves and highlighted solutions.

For the final 2 minutes, the coachee rejoined the circle to share what they have learnt.

Findings of Study: A post-troika questionnaire captured the trainees' experience of the exercise.

All trainees felt the exercise led to a meaningful conversation with their peers which resulted in mutual support.

7/9 trainees (78%) agreed that the exercise gave them novel solutions that they had not been aware of.

7/9 trainees (78%) felt empowered to tackle their challenge with more confidence.

All trainees felt they would use the troika exercise in the future.

Conclusions: The importance and gain of asking for guidance from readily accessible peers.

The Troika tool was associated with an increased feeling of empowerment and confidence in tackling challenges amongst trainees.

Coaching relationships did not need to be hierarchical to be effective.

The relationship of troika and whether it improves physician wellbeing will be a useful association to be explored further.

The Troika tool could be used in a variety of hospital and practice settings across disciplines in an integrative approach.

Key Words: Coaching, Wellbeing, teamwork

Biography

Dr Seher Ahmad is a Consultant Physician and Chair of Primary Care at Cleveland Clinic Abu Dhabi. She is also the Associate Program Director of the Internal Medicine Residency Program and Chair of the Clinical Competency Committee, leading on remediation efforts for residents. Dr Seher has completed a Post Graduate Certificate in Medical Education from the University of Manchester and in recognition of her contribution to graduate medical education was awarded Fellow of the Higher Education Academy (United Kingdom).

Dr Seher completed an MSc in Medical Leadership and Service Improvement and leads on implementing the Quality Improvement Curriculum for residents. Her research areas include:

1. Evidence-based remediation strategies
2. Curriculum development
3. Resident Wellbeing Interventions aimed at reducing stress and fostering professional growth.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Assessment of PG learners in Doctor of Medicine in Radiodiagnosis with reference to conduction of ultrasound examination using the Initiation Procedure Closure Checklist – a comparative pilot study*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Gaurav Vedprakash Mishra

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Anurag Ashok Luharia,
- Dr. Waqar Mohsin Raza Naqvi,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: As per NMC CBME guidelines of 2019(1), scheme of examination and assessment explicitly states under the heading of practical assessment - 'to perform ultrasound on a patient' with no suggested/standard steps/protocol.

Purpose & Objectives: Aim - To determine the efficacy of the Initiation Procedure Closure Checklist (2,3) in order to assess the Post Graduate learners in Doctor of Medicine in Radiodiagnosis with reference to conduction of ultrasound examination.

Objectives -

1. To assess the Post Graduate learners of Doctor of Medicine in Radiodiagnosis with reference to conduction of ultrasound on a subject using the conventional mode of assessment.
2. To assess the Post Graduate learners of Doctor of Medicine in Radiodiagnosis with reference to conduction of ultrasound on a subject using the Initiation Procedure Closure Checklist
3. To compare the results of assessment using conventional mode of assessment and Initiation Procedure Closure Checklist

Materials & Methods: Study setting - Department of Radiodiagnosis, JNMC, Wardha Study duration - 6 months

Study design - quasi experimental prospective case control study
Study participants - II and III year junior resident doctors

Sampling method - Convenient purposive sampling

Sample Size - 26 – 13 learners each batch (First-year residents excluded)

Group 1 (n=6) and 2 (n=7) was formed in a randomized manner for each batch.

Group 1 – conventional teaching without IPC Checklist(2,3), Group 2 – IPC Checklist,, both groups were directed to perform ultrasound examination of patients. Both groups from each batch were evaluated using the IPC Checklist (2,3). Informed consent was taken from the study participants.

Findings of Study: 100% students scored 100% marks in both conventional and IPC Checklist teaching methods for steps 5 to 13 as these were common in both methods. Statistical significant difference was observed in steps 1,2,3,4 and 14 for II year resident doctors whereas no statistical difference was observed in the same steps for III year resident doctors. Graphs 1 and 2 display the details below with regard to steps 1,2,3,4 and 14.

Conclusions: 1. Only sitting/Standing on the right side of the patient is not enough, but to start the conversation, you must greet the patient with a calm, compassionate and smiling face along with a cheerful voice/ tone. (step 1)

2. To obtain the relevant required history from the patient, instead of asking the patient directly about it, it is more proper to introduce yourself to the patient first, and then begin to establish a rapport with the patient. (step 2)

3. Always try to first observation and results explain the patient in brief regarding the procedure, which you are going to do/ perform on the patient so that the degree of apprehension on the patient's part is reduced, further increasing, the chances of patient cooperation along the procedure to be performed/ done. (step 3)

4. Despite, the patient, providing a written and signed consent to the referring clinician, the radiologist must be very particular about asking the patient for his/ her consent and/ or willingness for undergoing the said procedure to avoid any ethical breach, and at the same time, upholding the autonomy of the patient, which is one of the core principles of bioethics. (step 4)

5. After the examination/ procedure is complete, following proper documentation of relevant findings and submitting the duly signed report in the patient's hospital records, the radiologist must be very particular about describing the findings in brief to the patient in his/ her own vernacular language, excluding the medical jargon so that the established rapport gets a proper direction further and improves upon building of faith on the patient's part. (step 14)

Conclusion

The importance of building a rapport in between the examining radiologist, and the patient is essential and underscored in the study. Emphasis has been laid on the steps where initiation of the procedure is considered where in communication forms, the backbone of the entire procedure and lays the foundation of building of faith and confidence along with a possible sense of security in the heart and mind of the patient towards the examining radiologist.

Key Words: ultrasound, initiation, performance, closure, IPC checklist, radiology, postgraduate education, medical education

References: Guidelines for competency based post graduate training programme for MD in Radiodiagnosis, 2019, National Medical Commission, India.

Dr. Gaurav Mishra, Mr. Anurag Luharia. Initiation-Performance-Closure Checklist for ultrasound examination of subject IPCC a concept note. Diary Number 2 3673/2023-CO/L. ROC number L-135518/2023. Copyright Register of India.

Mishra, Gaurav Vedprakash; Luharia, Anurag A1. Initiation-performance-closure Checklist for Ultrasound Examination of Subject: Can this be Incorporated for Assessment?. Journal of Datta Meghe Institute of Medical Sciences University 18(4):p 591-592, Oct–Dec 2023. | DOI: 10.4103/jdmimsu.jdmimsu_669_23

Biography

I am Dr. Gaurav V Mishra, Professor in the subject of Radiodiagnosis at Jawaharlal Nehru medical College, presently serving as the sitting Pro Vice Chancellor of Datta Institute of higher education and research (deemed to be university), Maharashtra, India. I have completed my Ph.D. in Radiodiagnosis as well as another Ph.D. in Health Professions Education in 2018 and 2022 respectively. I have completed Masters in Health Professions Education in 2018. I have presently 92 publications in scopus, 65 publications in web of science and 33 publications in PubMed with some successful accepted articles, yet to get indexed in the said agencies. my core areas of research and work are radiology, radiological, physics, medical education, health professions, education with special emphasis and focus on curriculum, design, programme evaluation, assessment with innovations in teaching learning assessment methods also including artificial intelligence inclusion. I am presently member of Association for Study of Medical Education (ASME), member of Association of Medical Educators of Europe (AMEE) and also a member of International Association of Medical Science Educators (IAMSE). I am the international lead faculty for AMEE ESME courses in India with 4 internationally recognised centres. Recipient of IMA National Young Academic Excellence Award 2023.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Contextual Surprise Theory in Postgraduate Training and Assessment*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Dixon Thomas

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Pharmacy graduates were not showing practice readiness when they graduated. Within the undergraduate program, experiential education was added to introduce practice experience between the program, and more extensive training was included towards the end of the program. Still, practice readiness remains a concern. Those graduates who undergo postgraduate training like internship, residency, or fellowship also have some, but relatively less, practice readiness. New employees also experience issues in practice readiness that might extend from one to six months or even more for some of them. It is important to understand the core elements essentially contributing to practice readiness.

Purpose & Objectives: The purpose of this research was to create a framework that could explain the theoretical basis for concerns about practice readiness in postgraduate training. Understanding those concerns could mitigate the issue of practice readiness for postgraduate trainees more effectively. This research follows a constructivist paradigm and uses research questions rather than objectives. The research questions are as follows;

1. What elements of practice readiness are observed in a practice-ready pharmacy practitioner?
2. How could the gaps in postgraduate trainees' practice readiness be addressed in their learning and assessment?

Materials & Methods: This research uses a constructivist research paradigm and qualitative research methods. The methods include non-participant direct observation and in-depth semi-structured interviews of post-graduate trainees and their trainers. Multiple methods involving research participants different backgrounds were exercised for triangulation and validating the findings. Samples were included until no new themes were constructed and the codes fairly dense the themes. The researcher has an inside-outsider positionality, being a dispassionate observer with good access to the research site. Thematic analysis was used to interpret the data, assigning codes and themes in Atlas.ti software version 24 for Mac.

Findings of Study: The main theme co-constructed was the interconnection of a trainee within the system. Exposure to a new system in a new role at a new site, even for an experienced practitioner, adds an element of surprise that shall be resolved by sensing how the system works. Preparation is the next theme: understanding the system and knowing it works. The last theme is negotiation, like in communities of practice, theory to practice.

Conclusions: This research proposes Contextual Surprise Theory as a sub-theory to Communities of Practice. Understanding and managing contextual surprise as early as possible will help trainees prepare and negotiate their interventions contextually appropriate. Such authentic training will also help trainees develop their patterns of work and become experts at the site. Until then, the

assessment expectations need to be tailored to be fair to the trainee. Contextual Surprise is more of a concept that needs to be expanded as a theory.

Key Words: Contextual, Postgraduate, Training, Assessment

References: Etienne Wenger-Trayner, Mark Fenton O’Creevy, Steven Hutchinson, Chris Kubiak, Beverly Wenger-Trayner. Learning in landscapes of practice. Routledge, 2014.

Thomas D. Clinical pharmacy education, practice and research: clinical pharmacy, drug information, pharmacovigilance, pharmacoeconomics and clinical research. Elsevier; 2018.

Biography

I am a pharmacist academician by profession. I am also building my medical education profile. I have an MS in Education Management, a Graduate Diploma in Health Professions Education, and am currently pursuing my Doctor of Education. I am working as a Professor and Associate Dean-Clinical, responsible for experiential education at Gulf Medical University College of Pharmacy. I practice as Director of Drug Information Service at Thumbay University Hospital, the campus hospital of Gulf Medical University. The presentation is part of my EdD research.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Effect of different teaching/learning approaches using virtual patients on student's situational interest and cognitive load: a comparative study*

Presenter's Name: Prof. Sura Ali Ahmed Fuoad Al Bayati

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Walid El-Sayed,
- Dr. Hesham Marei,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Virtual Patients (VPs) have been receiving considerable attention in medical education as an authentic learning and teaching approach. In addition, and due to advancements in the fields of virtual reality and artificial intelligence,

more extensive applications of VPs in health profession education are expected. In the context of medical education, VPs can be defined as “an interactive

computer simulation of a real-life clinical scenario for teaching, learning, and assessment” [1].

Generally, there are two major distinguished categories or designs of VPs which are the ‘problem-solving’ and the ‘narrative’ approaches [2, 3]. For teaching clinical reasoning and diagnosis purposes, the problem-solving design is preferable in which students have to collect a range of information, usually from menus of possible history questions, lab tests, and physical examinations, and make diagnostic and management decisions based on their findings. While the narrative design is concerned with causeand-

effect purpose. This includes programs that have an emphasis on decision making which results in various outcomes over time [2, 3]. Furthermore, VPs can be classified according to the interaction of the learner with the VPs into linear and branched tree designs.

Situational interest can be defined as “an immediate affective response to certain conditions and/or stimuli in the learning environment that focuses one’s attention on the task, which may or may not last over time” [8]. It has been shown to be a good predictor of students engagement with learning activities and learning outcomes[8]. Instructional activities that are challenging,

novel, attracting for learner attention, offering the opportunity

for exploration, and be enjoyable have been shown

to be triggers of situational interest [9]. Cognitive load can also influence learning outcomes.

Cognitive load is managing the capacity of working memory, so it can process novel information to construct schemas in long-term memory [12]. Cognitive load can be classified into three types: intrinsic, extraneous,

and germane [13]. Extraneous cognitive load is concerned with the instructional method used to present the educational material. While the intrinsic cognitive load is concerned with the inherent difficulty and complexity of the knowledge that needs to be acquired.

However, there is still a need for more research about the effectiveness of different teaching/learning approaches using VPs regarding the cognitive load and situational interest of the students. Also, more research needs to be conducted to see the best way to use VPs to achieve the maximum benefits of their educational purpose whether it is used alone or in a collaborative session with other methods of teaching.

Purpose & Objectives: to find an answer to the following research question “Would Situational Interest and cognitive load differ when a VPs session about maxillofacial trauma is conducted individually and preceded by a lecture about the same topic,

compared to the same VPs session conducted as an interactive and collaborative session within the lecture?”

Materials & Methods: Methods

The study design was an Experimental comparative study that was conducted at Gulf Medical University -UAE. The study was reviewed and approved by the University Ethical Committee IRB Ref. no. RB/MHPE/STD/20/Dec- 2020. Students were either exposed to a lecture followed by an independent VPs session (Group 1, n: 69) or to a single collaborative VPs session within a lecture (Group 2, n: 70). Lecture and VPs sessions were about the same topic. All the dental students were in their 4th academic year (semester 8) of a 5-year discipline-based dental program. During this academic year, students are exposed to the oral surgery discipline in which the study was conducted on one of its topics. Exclusion criteria: students who missed one of the two sessions and students who did not complete the full questionnaire. Virtual patients For the teaching and learning sessions, one branching tree VPs designed with a single end node was used. In this type of design, multiple learner pathways are used which allows learners to choose between asking for a lab result or confirming the diagnosis and moving forward with the analysis. The learner pathway is based on the decisions taken by the learner at every strategic node [4]. The VPs are in the form of E-learning scorm package that is uploaded on Moodle and used by the instructor and learners. These VPs were based 3 clinical cases of real patient scenarios different types of maxillofacial injuries. Real patient radiographs, lab results, intra-oral photos, and records for other special investigations were used at different stages of the VPs path, while two-dimensional graphics (Two-dimensional graphics means using regular videos and image technology and not three-D technology) were used to represent different clinical settings and

different characters within the VPs. The main purpose of VPs was to teach and learn problems related to maxillofacial trauma. Diagnosis and treatment planning of mandibular fractures were the main goals of the session. All the participants worked with the same cases.

Procedure The first cohort (Group1) received a lecture followed by a learning session using one independent VPs while the other cohort (Group 2) received the discussion-based session (collaborative session) in which VPs are a part of the contents of the interactive lecture. All interventions were delivered by the same subject expert.

1- Lecture followed by independent VPs sessions (Group1): All students received the same lecture which was about maxillofacial trauma in the oral and maxillofacial regions. The lecture was conducted for 40 minutes as a PowerPoint presentation. The lecture followed a teacher-centred approach and targeted the learning objectives mainly related to the diagnosis of specific conditions through identifying the relevant history, signs and symptoms, and the required investigations. After

that students take 20 minutes' rest and then they had VPs as an independent activity for 40 minutes. Students were asked to use their laptops to answer the VPs session independently.

2- VPs Collaborative session (Group 2): A single session,

in which VPs were conducted as a collaborative interactive activity within the lecture for 40 minutes. The VPs were projected on the classroom screen using a data show projector. The role of the tutor was to facilitate the session by asking why specific decisions were taken, what the consequence would be of choosing other options, providing feedback, and finally operating the VPs based on the decisions taken. During this session, students were allowed to go into a discussion with other students to reach the final consensus. Questioners For the cognitive load, the study used the cognitive load questionnaire developed and validated by Leppink, Paas, van Gog, van der Vleuten, and van Merriënboer (2013) [17]. The language of the study is English, and the students are international students who are native speakers" so there was no need to change or modify the questioners. For measuring the intrinsic and extraneous cognitive load. It was an 8-item assessment, example of such items" The content of this lecture was very complex" & "the problem/s covered in this lecture was very complex", the questionnaire was given at the end of each teaching session, and it was measured on a Likert scale from 1- to10 [17]. The situational interest was a 6-item assessment which

was validated before by another researcher Rotgans and Schmidt, 2017 [18], example of such items "I want to know more about this topic" & "I enjoy working on this topic" The situational interest questionnaire was given during the session every 10 minutes during conducting the different teaching sessions and it was measured on a Likert scale from 1 to 5. All the Questioners were answered on paper during face-to-face sessions. Statistical analysis Data were collected and analysed using SPSS software (IBM SPSS 27.0, SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA). The data is considered ordinal data. Scores on each of the 6 SI and 8 Cognitive questions were summed for each participant, and the median was subsequently calculated for each group. After that, the median was compared using a nonparametric test (inferential tests). Friedman Repeated (ANOVA Test) and Wilcoxon signed-rank test (Pairwise comparison) were used for intragroup comparison. While Mann-Whiney U test (Pairwise comparison) and Kruskal Wallis test were used for intergroup comparison. In this study, the Significance level was set at $p < .05$. Findings of Study: Results Two dental cohorts have participated in the study; the first cohort includes 69 students ($n = 69$) and the second cohort includes 70 students ($n = 70$). All participants completed their tasks, so no one was excluded with a respondent rate of 100%. The average age is 18-21 years old and 35% male and 65% female. Situational interest – intragroup comparison

Group 1: Comparing the situational interest scores at different time points during the lecture session showed no significant difference between the median score at repeated time points . However, there was a significant difference between the median score at repeated time points during conducting the independent VPs session.

Group 2: Collaborative VPs session showed no significant difference between the median score at repeated time points. Following these results, the independent VPs session showed a negative median rank difference from 10 minutes to 20 minutes indicating that students showed high interest at the 10 minutes and this difference was significant (p value:0.012). The test showed also a positive median rank difference of situational interest from 20 minutes to 30 minutes. This means that the situational interest started to decline from 20 minutes to 30 minutes, but not significantly (p -value 0.116. The decline, however, was significant between 30 minutes and 40 minutes

(p-value: < 0.001) . Situational interest – intersessions comparison at 10 minutes, the VPs' collaborative session showed a high median score of situational interest than both lecture and independent VPs sessions, and the difference was significant (p-value: < 0.033). But no significant difference between a lecture and independent VPs sessions (Fig. 1).

At 20 minutes, there was no significant difference between all the sessions, although the lecture session showed a low median score of situational interest than both VPs independent and VPs collaborative sessions.

At 30 minutes, the VPs collaborative session showed a high median score of situational interest than both lecture and VPs independent sessions, and the difference was significant (p-value: 0.002), and there was no significant difference between lecture and independent VPs sessions. At 40 minutes, the VPs interactive session showed an again high median score of situational interest than both the lecture and VPs independent session, and the difference was significant. However, the difference was also significant between the lecture and independent VPs sessions (p-value: < 0.001) . Cognitive load The total cognitive load was found to be lowest in the VPs collaborative session, and highest in the lecture session. However, this difference was not significant Intrinsic cognitive load was a little high in the VPs collaborative session than in both lecture and independent VPs sessions, however, this difference was not significant. The results also showed that the collaborative VPs session has the lowest extraneous cognitive load than the independent VPs and lecture sessions and this difference was a significant difference with P-value equal to 0.000 (P < 0.001).

Conclusions: Our study suggested that using VPs in a collaborative learning activity enhances students' situational interest with minimal investment in cognitive load than its use as an independent learning activity after the lecture.

Key Words: Virtual patient, Situational interest, Cognitive load

References: -Marei HF, Donkers J, Al-Eraky MM, Van Merrienboer JJG. Collaborative use of virtual patients after a lecture enhances learning with minimal investment of cognitive load. Med Teach. 2019;41(3):332–9.

-Marei HF, Donkers J, Al-Eraky MM, Van Merrienboer JJG. Collaborative use of virtual patients after a lecture enhances learning with minimal investment of cognitive load. Med Teach. 2019;41(3):332–9.

Biography

Master's in Health profession education (Cen MEDIC FAIMER DL) in 2021.

- Doctoral Degree in Oral Medicine (Ph D), Baghdad university, Iraq ,2005.
- Master Degree in Oral Medicine (M Sc) , Baghdad university, Iraq ,1995.
- Bachelor Degree of Oral and Dental Medicine and Surgery (BDS) , Baghdad university, Iraq ,1988
- ICDL, UNISCO, 2010 (Jordan).
- A faculty of college of dentistry since 1988, in Baghdad university, Iraq, up to date in Gulf medical university, UAE.

- Associate Dean College of Dentistry, Gulf medical university since 2012-2019.
- professor of Oral medicine with MOH license.
- Many publications in oral medicine and other dentistry field in national and international journals of high impact factor.
- Member of curriculum, inter-professional education and community engagement committees in college of dentistry, member of college council in in college of dentistry and GMU.
- Year 5 coordinator and mentor of group of dental students. Mentor for dentistry student
- Specialist in Oral medicine-MOH, 2014.
- Reviewer in many scientific dental journals.
- Currently lead faculty in 6 courses and member in 5 courses in BDS curriculum, faculty member in Master of health profession education program in GMU.
- Supervise Master thesis in public health.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *AI Chatbots Show Promise But Limitations on UK Medical Exam Questions: A Comparative Performance Study*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Mohamad Monif Assker

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Mohammed Ahmed Sadeq,
- Dr. Mohamed Hady Ashry,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT have potential applications in medical education, but require evaluation on complex tasks like medical licensing exams.

Purpose & Objectives: The purpose of this study was to evaluate how well publicly accessible LLMs performed on simulated UK medical board exam questions.

Materials & Methods: 423 board-style questions from 9 UK exams (MRCS, MRCP, etc.) were answered by seven LLMs (ChatGPT-3.5, ChatGPT-4, Bard, Perplexity, Claude, Bing, Claude Instant). There were 406 multiple-choice, 13 true/false, and 4 "choose N" questions covering topics in surgery, pediatrics, and other disciplines. The accuracy of the output was graded. Statistics were used to analyze differences among LLMs.

Findings of Study: Average scores were: ChatGPT-4 (78.7%), Bing (66.9%), Claude (65.2%), Claude Instant (62.9%), ChatGPT-3.5 (61.7%), Bard (58.9%), and Perplexity (57.4%). Scores differed significantly between LLMs overall (p

Conclusions: LLMs demonstrated limitations in answering certain complex question types, indicating refinements needed before primary reliance in medical education. However, their expanding capabilities suggest a potential to improve training if thoughtfully implemented. Further research should explore specialty-specific LLMs and optimal integration into medical curricula.

Key Words: Large language models, Medical licensing exams, Medical Education

References: Alabed Alrazak, S., & Sheikh, J. (2023). Large Language Models in Medical Education: Opportunities, Challenges, and Future Directions. *JMIR Medical Education*, 9, e48291. <https://doi.org/10.2196/48291>

Bhayana, R., Krishna, S., & Bleakney, R. R. (2023). Performance of ChatGPT on a Radiology Boardstyle Examination: Insights into Current Strengths and

Limitations. *Radiology*, 307(5), e230582. <https://doi.org/10.1148/radiol.230582>

Biography

With great enthusiasm and a strong commitment to excellence, I am eager to embark on a professional journey as both a Radiology Resident and an experienced author. Leveraging valuable research experience gained through academic and professional endeavors, I have actively engaged in

numerous projects in an effort to have a positive impact on my community. Alongside a deep understanding of clinical science and medical fundamentals, I have honed a versatile skill set that includes lecturing, creative writing, translation, proficiency in Microsoft Office, and graphic design. The driving force behind my aspirations is the opportunity to contribute my diverse expertise, shaping impactful projects and making a significant difference in the healthcare field.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Impact of Online Expert Interview-Based Research Training Course on Perceived Knowledge and Confidence Among Medical Trainees*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Fikri M Abu-Zidan

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Arif Alper Cevik,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: The COVID-19 Pandemic, which limited trainees' access to hospitals, had also disrupted traditional research training [1, 2]. The International Emergency Medicine Education Project introduced the online Fundamentals of Research in Medicine course to support trainees during the pandemic.

Purpose & Objectives: This study assesses the course's effect on participants' perceived knowledge and confidence in research concepts.

Materials & Methods: A prospective observational study. Pre- and post-course surveys measured participants' perceived knowledge and confidence levels across 16 research-related topics. Quantitative survey data were analysed using the Wilcoxon Signed-Rank test, and qualitative feedback was evaluated to explore participants' experiences.

Findings of Study: A total of 272 participants enrolled in the course. 168 participants started, and 52 (19.2%) completed the pre- and post-surveys and the course completion exam. Medical students and interns, as well as participants from Africa and Asia, comprised the majority. Most participants were from India. 78.8% of the participants were from low-income or lower-middle-income countries. Participants' perceived knowledge and confidence significantly improved after completing the course, p

Conclusions: The online course, designed as an interview format, effectively enhanced participants' perceived research knowledge and confidence. Future studies should incorporate objective measures of research skill acquisition from online courses and evaluate the long-term impact on participants' academic and professional development.

Key Words: Research training, Online education, Perceived knowledge, Confidence improvement, Medical trainees

References: 1. TMS Collaborative. The perceived impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on medical student education and training - an international survey. *BMC Med Educ.* 2021; doi:10.1186/s12909-021-02983-3

2. Walters M, Alonge T, Zeller M. Impact of COVID-19 on Medical Education: Perspectives from Students. *Acad Med.* 2022; doi:10.1097/ACM.0000000000004525

Biography

Professor Fikri Abu-Zidan: An international expert in Statistics, Research Methodology, Acute Care Surgery, Disaster Medicine, and Point-of-Care Ultrasound. He graduated (MD) from Aleppo University (Syria) in 1981; gained the FRCS, Glasgow, Scotland in 1987; achieved his PhD in Trauma and Disaster Medicine from Linkoping University (Sweden) in 1995; and obtained his Postgraduate Diploma of Applied Statistics from Massey University (New Zealand) in 1999. He is currently serving as a Statistics and Research Methodology Consultant for the World Society of Emergency Surgery. He has made major contributions to trauma and acute care surgery management, education and research in Kuwait, Sweden, New Zealand, Australia, and United Arab Emirates. He has more than 515 publications in books and refereed international journals. He presented more than 830 invited lectures and scientific abstracts, chaired more than 80 scientific sessions, and received more than 40 national and international awards for clinical, research and educational activities.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Integrating Research Training in Medical Internship at Dubai Health : Our Experience and Outcomes*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Ayesha Saeed Almheiri

Co-Authors:

- Dr. Sara Almarzooqi,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Incorporating a research curriculum into the medical internship program enhances interns' research skills and promotes an evidence-based approach to clinical practice. By guiding interns through each step of the research process, we aim to foster critical thinking, collaboration, and scientific writing skills, equipping them for future clinical and academic roles.

Purpose & Objectives: The primary purpose of this curriculum was to provide medical interns with a structured and mentored research experience that enhances their skills in proposal development, ethical research practices, data analysis, and manuscript writing. This framework aims to prepare interns for lifelong learning and evidence-based clinical decision-making.

Materials & Methods: The research curriculum was designed around a structured process, with pre-selected research topics aligned with clinical relevance and feasibility. Each intern group was assigned a dedicated supervisor to provide focused mentorship throughout the research journey. Key curriculum components included:

- **Proposal Development:** Intern groups were tasked with writing research proposals, highlighting objectives, methods, and anticipated outcomes. Each group was allotted two weeks to develop and finalize their proposal.
- **IRB Application:** After drafting the proposal, groups submitted their applications to the Institutional Review Board (IRB) for approval within the same two-week period. This fast-tracked timeline emphasized efficiency in administrative processes.
- **Data Collection:** Utilizing secondary data, interns focused on data analysis to minimize the logistical challenges associated with primary data collection while reinforcing skills in data handling and interpretation.
- **Manuscript Writing:** The final phase involved drafting a research paper to synthesize findings and practice scientific communication. Supervisors guided interns on structure, clarity, and adherence to academic standards.

Findings of Study: Challenges and Solutions

Time constraints and varied levels of research experience among interns presented initial challenges. To address this, supervisors provided templates for proposal writing and step-by-step guidance for IRB applications, reducing uncertainties and ensuring a smoother progression through each stage.

Outcomes and Feedback

Preliminary feedback from interns and supervisors suggests the curriculum successfully improved research understanding and practical skills. Interns reported increased confidence in navigating research processes, from ethical considerations to data analysis and manuscript preparation. Supervisors appreciated the structure of the program, which facilitated focused mentorship and timely project completion.

Conclusions: This structured, guided research curriculum for medical interns demonstrated feasibility and effectiveness in promoting essential research skills. By building research competencies early in their careers, we anticipate these interns will carry forward an analytical mindset into their clinical practice. Future iterations of this curriculum may explore expanding topic variety and extending timelines based on individual project requirements.

Key Words: Medical Internship, Research Curriculum, Proposal Writing, IRB Application, Secondary Data Analysis.

References: Khan, K. S., & Coomarasamy, A. (2006). A hierarchy of effective teaching and learning to acquire competence in evidenced-based medicine. *BMC Medical Education*, 6(1), 59.
doi:10.1186/1472-6920-6-59

Al-Habib, D. K., Qayumi, A. K., McLaughlin, K., & Antoniou, S. A. (2020). Developing research competencies in medical trainees. *Journal of Surgical Education*, 77(4), 890-895.
doi:10.1016/j.jsurg.2019.11.005

Biography

Dr. Ayesha AlMheiri is a dedicated Family Medicine Specialist, Medical Internship Program Director, and chair of training. She earned her Arab Board and MRCGP certifications in Family Medicine in 2021, a foundation that has fueled her commitment to both clinical practice and medical education. Her passion for teaching led her to complete a degree in Leadership in Health Profession Education in 2020, a milestone that shaped her philosophy around learner-centered education.

As an educator, Dr. AlMheiri integrates active learning methods like Team-Based Learning (TBL), Case-Based Learning (CBL), and Problem-Based Learning (PBL) into her teaching. Her journey began as a Clinical Lecturer at MBRU, where she guided students through interactive TBL sessions. In 2021, she became a core faculty member in the Family Medicine residency, redesigning educational activities to foster self-directed learning and critical thinking.

Since her appointment as Medical Internship Program Director in 2023, Dr. AlMheiri has ensured trainees receive exceptional training across multiple clinical sites, emphasizing mentorship and high-quality assessments.

Date of Presentation: 15 & 16 Feb. 2025

Time of the Presentation: 1:40 PM - 2:40 PM & 12:15 PM - 1:15 PM

Location of the Presentation: Saqr Ballroom C

Title: *Enhancing Medical Expertise in the New Normal: Effectiveness of Continuing Medical Education Among Allied Healthcare Professionals*

Presenter's Name: Dr. Noof mohamed Althawadi

Co-Authors:

Dr. Wiam Elshami,

Abstract

Background & Introduction: Continuing Medical Education (CME) plays a pivotal role in ensuring the ongoing professional development and competency of Allied healthcare professionals (HCPs). With the advent of COVID-19 pandemic, the delivery of CME activities underwent significant shift towards online learning. In order to assure effective CME activities and improve participants' satisfaction in the new normal, it is crucial to understand the most preferred educational format by HCPs.

Purpose & Objectives: This study aims to (1) explore HCPs' perspectives on the effectiveness, challenges, and recommendations for CME delivery methods, in the new normal, post COVID-19 pandemic. (2) assess the most effective educational format for addressing CME's in the new normal and factors influencing the quality of online and face-to-face learning experiences.

Materials & Methods: A qualitative study utilizing focus group discussions to gather insights from participants. Thematic analysis was conducted to identify recurring themes.

Findings of Study: Majority of participants expressed a preference for face-to-face interactions, particularly for hands-on practical sessions, they also acknowledged the importance of online. Participants advocated for a blended learning approach that combines elements of both online and face-to-face modalities. Blended learning offers flexibility, accessibility, and scalability, while also providing opportunities for hands-on experiences and interactive learning.

Conclusions: The study highlights the complex landscape of CME delivery methods and the need for a balanced approach that leverages the strengths of both online and face-to-face learning modalities. By continually evaluating and refining educational approaches, healthcare professionals can ensure ongoing professional development and competency, ultimately enhancing patient care outcomes.

Key Words: Continuing Medical Education; Online learning; blended learning

References: Alkhazim, M., Althubaiti, A., Al-Ateeg, H., Alkhwaiter, M., & AlNasser, M. (2015). Delivering Effective Continuous Medical Education in Saudi Arabia: Some Critical Issues. *Health Professions Education*, 1(1), 43-49. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.hpe.2015.11.002>

Kalnow, A., Beck-Esmay, J., Riddell, J., Casey, J., Carlson, J. N., Rezaie, S. R., & Little, A. (2021). Continuing medical education delivery preferences among physicians and advanced practice providers in emergency medicine. *Cureus*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.20406>

Biography

I am Noof Mohamed Althawadi, a healthcare professional from Bahrain with an outstanding academic and professional background. I hold a Bachelor's degree in Medical Diagnostic Imaging from the University of Sharjah in the United Arab Emirates, where I graduated with the highest honors.

Driven to further my education, I went on to earn a Master of Science (MSc) degree in Leadership in Health Profession Education from the University of Sharjah, UAE, in collaboration with the University of East Anglia in the United Kingdom. Again, I graduated with the highest honors.

Currently, I am pursuing a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Health Professions Education at the University of Maastricht in the Netherlands, demonstrating my relentless pursuit of knowledge and skills in the healthcare field.

Since 2021, I have been working as an educator and radiographer at the Mohammed bin Khalifa Cardiac Center in Bahrain, where I continue to contribute to the medical community. My research interests focus on enhancing the competency clinical mentors and evaluating the effectiveness of continuous medical education delivery. I have presented my research at conferences such as the UAEGSRC 2023 and the TUFH 2023 conference, and have published one research paper with others in progress.

